

1 Highlights

2 **Implementation of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning-Based Methods**
3 **in Brain-Computer Interaction**

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- 6 • A thorough review of artificial intelligence and machine learning-based methods in
7 brain-computer interfaces.
- 8 • Comprehensive description of invasive and non-invasive types of brain-computer inter-
9 faces.
- 10 • Summary on the most current artificial intelligence and machine learning-based solu-
11 tions applied for processing, analysis and interpretation of brain signals.
- 12 • Comparison of individual algorithms, summary of important findings and recommen-
13 dations for future research in brain-computer interface systems.

Implementation of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning-Based Methods in Brain-Computer Interaction

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Abstract

Brain-computer interfaces are used for direct two-way communication between the human brain and the computer. Brain signals contain valuable information about the mental state and brain activity of the examined subject. However, due to their non-stationarity and susceptibility to various types of interference, their processing, analysis and interpretation are challenging. For these reasons, the research in the field of brain-computer interfaces is focused on the implementation of artificial intelligence, especially in five main areas: calibration, noise suppression, communication, mental condition estimation, and motor imagery. The use of algorithms based on artificial intelligence and machine learning has proven to be very promising in these application domains, especially due to their ability to predict and learn from previous experience. Therefore, their implementation within medical technologies can contribute to more accurate information about the mental state of subjects, alleviate the consequences of serious diseases or improve the quality of life of disabled patients.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, artificial neural networks, brain-computer interfaces, fuzzy logic, machine learning, nature-inspired optimization techniques.

1. Introduction

Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) are powerful neural system-based interfaces, which connect the brain with a computer and allow their two-way communication [1, 2]. The BCI

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33 principle is based on the brain signals measurement, which are then sent to a computer
34 system, analyzed and, depending on the application area, used for user state monitoring
35 or communication and/or control [1]. These systems have been utilized in many areas,
36 particularly in healthcare, where the BCI research is focused on abnormal brain structures
37 and functions detection that can lead to the diagnosis of various diseases, sleep disorders,
38 or to predict epileptic seizures [3]. Another important area is rehabilitation, where the
39 BCIs can be used to restore the original level of mobility, minimize the consequences of
40 injuries or at least help the affected patient with daily life activities [4]. As far as non-
41 medical areas are concerned, the most promising applications for BCIs include use in the
42 field of neuroergonomics [5] and smart environment, the neuromarketing and advertisement,
43 or neurogaming and entertainment. Also, it is popular to use BCIs for emotion recognition
44 [6] or fatigue detection [7].

45 Registering the electrical activity of the human brain using the electroencephalography
46 (EEG) was first described and measured in the 1920s. Nevertheless, the research into the
47 development of BCIs began much later, specifically in the 1970s [8]. Very fast transmission,
48 conversion and processing of brain signals, enabling communication between the user and the
49 computer in real-time, were a necessary prerequisite for the emergence of BCIs. Thanks to
50 advances in science and technology in the 1960s, this real-time communication was possible,
51 and nothing stood in the way of the development of BCIs [2, 8]. The first research on BCIs
52 was conducted on animals (monkeys) [9], and testing of BCIs in human volunteers did not
53 spread until the 1990s [2]. The first successes of BCIs include research into controlling the
54 cursor on a computer screen or moving electric arm by consciously changing brain activity
55 [2, 8].

56 The BCI systems can be based on different methods since the human brain activity can
57 be acquired by a number of techniques, both invasive or non-invasive ones. In invasive mea-
58 surements, the electrical activity is sensed from the cortical surface by electrocorticography
59 (ECoG) or intracortically (iCor) from within the cortical tissue. In contrast, in non-invasive
60 measurements, the activity is sensed from the scalp surface directly or indirectly [2, 10]. The
61 *direct* measurements include sensing the electrical activity of nerve cells using conventional
62 EEG or sensing the magnetic fields generated by electric currents produced by the human
63 brain in the form of magnetoencephalography (MEG) [1]. The *indirect* measurements can be
64 performed using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and functional near-infrared
65 spectroscopy (fNIRS) [8, 11].

66 Using the BCI systems based on these techniques, clinically relevant information on a
67 patient's health state can be extracted, the consequences of serious illnesses can be mitigated
68 or patients' quality of life can be improved, either through smart medical devices or smart
69 homes [1, 2, 12, 13, 14, 10]. However, it is very computationally demanding to process,
70 analyze, and interpret these brain signals by conventional algorithms. This is mainly due to
71 their non-linear and non-stationary nature. In addition, the frequency range and amplitude
72 of brain signals are very low and the signal is often contaminated with various types of
73 artifacts [15, 16, 17]. The most recent research [18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 17, 24, 25] has
74 shown that algorithms based on artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are
75 very promising for processing and analyzing these complex signals, especially due to their

76 capability to predict, reason and learn from previous experience.

77 1.1. Structure of this Review

78 This paper focuses on the use of AI and ML algorithms in the field of BCI systems,
79 summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of the implemented methods and indicates
80 future challenges that should be further addressed. The structure of the review includes
81 Section 2, which provides a description of the architecture of BCI systems and a general
82 overview of both, non-invasive and invasive variants of BCIs. Section 3 focuses on the
83 description of five main application areas: calibration, noise suppression, communication,
84 mental condition estimation and motor imagery (MI). Section 4 compares the effectiveness of
85 the algorithms presented, highlights the most important findings and outlines the remaining
86 challenges that need to be addressed in BCI systems and AI- and ML-based algorithms.
87 The conclusion of the paper is provided in Section 5.

88 1.2. Literature Search Strategy

89 The most popular search engines such as: Google Scholar, PubMed and Scopus were
90 used to find and select relevant literature for this review. Phrases combining terms from the
91 area of BCIs were used in the search: "EEG-based BCI", "MEG-based BCI", "fNIRS-based
92 BCI", "fMRI-based BCI", "ECoG-based BCI" and "iCor-based BCI" along with terms from
93 AI and ML areas: "Artificial intelligence", "Machine learning", "Artificial neural network",
94 "Fuzzy logic", "Nature-inspired algorithm" and "Classification". Altogether, 36 queries were
95 used, as shown in Fig. 1. Only recent journal papers, published between 2010 and 2022,
were used in this review (all conference papers were excluded).

Figure 1: The procedure for seeking the relevant literature used in this review.

96

97 2. Brain-Computer Interfaces

98 As in other areas of human life, BCI systems have developed rapidly in recent years,
99 mainly due to advances in digital technology. Designing a reliable BCI device is a relatively
100 complex task that requires multidisciplinary knowledge in technical areas such as engineering
101 and signal processing, but also in neuroscience and psychology [26]. The use of the BCI
102 system involves two main phases: the first contains the offline phase, in which the BCI
103 system is calibrated, and the online phase, in which the measurement of brain activity itself
104 takes place [27]. A typical BCI system is represented by a closed loop, in which four main
105 steps are generally performed [28, 27]:

- 106 1. *Brain activity measurement* – The signal acquisition unit is used to record brain signals.
107 Both invasive and non-invasive approaches are used.
- 108 2. *Signal processing* – Brain signal processing includes filtering to remove unwanted inter-
109 ference and artifacts, feature extraction to describe brain signals using several relevant
110 properties, and classification to assign a class to a set of extracted features.
- 111 3. *Translation into a command* – Linking brain activity to a specific command and trans-
112 mitting that command to the output device. The command is used to invoke an action
113 within an external device.
- 114 4. *Feedback* – The user is provided with feedback, which informs them about the brain
115 activity patterns detected and helps them to improve control over the BCI.

116 In terms of the type of brain activity, BCIs can be divided into three groups:

- 117 (a) active:
118 the device is controlled by direct and conscious brain activity (independent of external
119 stimulation) [29].
- 120 (b) reactive:
121 the device is controlled indirectly, by brain signals generated in response to external
122 stimulation [30]. These can be, for example, cognitive, motor or sensory external
123 stimuli [28, 15].
- 124 (c) passive:
125 no mental effort is required on the part of the user. BCIs only monitor and quantify
126 the user’s mental state in real-time and adapt the application accordingly [31, 32, 25]

127 The BCI systems can be further divided according to the signal acquisition technique
128 used [2, 33]. A general overview of the BCI system according to this division, including
129 both, non-invasive and invasive techniques, is provided in this section and a general block
130 diagram of BCI system is presented in Fig. 2.

131 2.1. *Non-Invasive Brain-Computer Interfaces*

132 Non-invasive BCIs are generally very safe techniques that do not involve any disruption
133 of brain tissues. For this reason, these approaches are often used for long-term monitoring,
134 not only in clinical settings but also in science and research. The disadvantages of non-
135 invasive techniques include the lower signal quality and poorer spatial resolution compared
136 to invasive methods [2, 28, 33, 34, 35, 36]:

- 137 1. *Electroencephalography* – EEG-based BCIs are one of the most commonly used systems
138 for recording brain activity. These brain signals are sensed by surface electrodes usually
139 built into a special snug cap [37, 35, 38, 36]. The distribution of electrodes on the
140 surface of the scalp is uniform, most often according to the so-called 10 – 20 system.
141 The name of the system is based on the distances between the electrodes, which are

Figure 2: Block diagram of a general BCI system incorporating both invasive and non-invasive techniques for brain activity measurement.

10% or 20% of the scalp diameter. The 10 – 20 system uses a total of 21 electrodes: 19 located on the surface of the scalp and 2 on the earlobes as a reference [15]. There are also modified versions of the 10 – 20 system, such as 10 – 10 or 10 – 5 systems, where the arrangement of the electrodes is more dense [2, 36]. The basic frequency bands that can be encountered in the human EEG signal include the following [15, 37, 2]:

- **delta** (0.5 – 4 Hz): representing the deeper phase of sleep,
- **theta** (4 – 8 Hz): occurring in the initial phase of sleep,
- **alpha** (8 – 13 Hz): appearing in resting brain activity,
- **beta** (13 – 30 Hz): present in nervous subjects,
- **gamma** (30 – 80 Hz): manifesting themselves as a response to various stimuli.

The simplicity of measurement and relatively high temporal resolution are the advantages of the EEG technique. The main disadvantages of the EEG signal include very low spatial resolution and very low amplitude of the useful signal (around $100\mu\text{V}$) [15, 1, 36]. In addition, the measured EEG signal is often contaminated with various types of artifacts (movement artifacts, eye blinking, cardiac signal, breathing, etc.) leading to a very low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [39, 40].

2. *Magnetoencephalography* – MEG-based BCIs record magnetic fields induced by electric currents that arise during brain activity. Measurements are most often performed by means of magnetometers using a highly sensitive superconducting quantum interference device [41, 42, 43]. MEG signals are usually measured while sitting or lying by inserting the head into a stationary magnetometric system with the sensor coils [44, 42, 43].

164 Signals measured by MEG carry the same information as EEG, but with MEG it
165 is possible to capture the signals of a higher quality (i.e. with higher SNR values),
166 as there is no distortion due to skull layers, as in the case of measuring electrical
167 signals [45, 42, 46]. Financial costs, equipment complexity and non-portability are
168 disadvantages of MEG. Measurements must be performed in a magnetically shielded
169 room in the presence of trained staff [1, 45, 46]. For more practical use of MEG
170 technology, the current research [47] focuses on the development of wearable optically-
171 pumped magnetometers, which do not require magnetic shielding or cryogenic cooling.

172 3. *Functional near-infrared spectroscopy* – fNIRS-based BCIs are techniques based on
173 an optical approach that uses near-infrared light to monitor cortical hemodynamic
174 activity [48, 11, 33]. Caps, similar to those used for EEG acquisition, are used for
175 measurements. But instead of sensing electrodes, fNIRS caps are equipped with a
176 miniaturized light-emitting diode and light detectors (photodiodes) to capture back-
177 scattered (reflected) light [49, 45, 11]. Wavelengths in the range of 600–1000 nm, which
178 haemoglobin can significantly absorb and provide reliable information on changes in
179 haemoglobin concentration, are most commonly used [2, 50]. Nerve activity is then
180 estimated by measuring the amount of the light reflected and, thus, the changes in the
181 concentration of oxygenated and deoxygenated haemoglobin molecules [48, 51]. Low
182 costs and portability are the advantages of this technique. The measurement is simple
183 and suitable for research purposes. Compared to EEG, its disadvantages include the
184 response time for the commands execution and worse temporal resolution [1, 52].

185 4. *Functional magnetic resonance imaging* – fMRI-based BCIs map brain activity accord-
186 ing to the local changes in cortical oxygenation and perfusion through electromagnetic
187 fields. Since the use of a particular area of the brain requires an increase in blood flow,
188 blood oxygenation level-dependent contrast is used for measurement [53, 2]. This type
189 of contrast imaging is able to detect dynamic changes in neuronal activity caused
190 by local fluctuations in the oxyhaemoglobin and deoxyhaemoglobin ratio [53]. The
191 measurement procedure is similar to the conventional MRI scanner examination [45].
192 High spatial resolution and the ability to capture information from deeper parts of the
193 brain that cannot be measured by EEG or MEG are an advantage of fMRI-based BCIs
194 [1, 54, 55]. Low temporal resolution, financial costs, large dimensions of the measuring
195 device, the need to magnetically shield the room and the necessary presence of trained
196 staff are the limitations of this technique [2, 54].

197 2.2. *Invasive Brain-Computer Interfaces*

198 In contrast to non-invasive approaches, invasive variants of BCIs undergo surgical inser-
199 tion of sensing electrodes into the brain. The risk of infection is, therefore, a limitation of
200 these methods, but, on the other hand, it is possible to obtain better signals with higher
201 spatial resolution [2, 28, 10, 34, 56]. And these are following:

202 1. *Intracortical technique* – As for measurement, iCor-based BCIs use a single electrode
203 or an array of electrodes located inside the cerebral cortex [1, 57, 10]. The electrodes

204 are placed very close to the source of the signal to be measured. Since this is an
205 invasive variant, it is possible to measure better quality signals with higher amplitude
206 than in the case of scalp EEG [1, 2, 34].

207 A signal recorded with a high SNR value, a very high temporal and spatial resolution
208 and the ability to accurately locate the signal source are the advantages of this method.
209 The disadvantages include the need for a surgical intervention and the associated risk
210 of infection or other damage. In addition, once the measuring electrodes are implanted,
211 it is not possible to change their position [1].

- 212 2. *Electrocorticography* – ECoG-based BCIs are a less invasive variant of measuring brain
213 activity compared to iCor-based BCIs. When measuring ECoG, implantable strips or
214 grids are placed on the surface of the cerebral cortex, under the dura mater [15, 2, 10].
215 The strips and grids are made of flexible materials to minimize the risk of mechanical
216 brain injury [58]. Electrode insertion can take place under general or local anaesthesia
217 [59].

218 Despite the lower invasiveness, a similar quality signal with a high SNR value and
219 high both temporal and spatial resolution, as in the case of iCor-based BCIs, can be
220 obtained using ECoG [45]. Moreover, it is possible to record low-voltage components
221 that cannot be detected by scalp EEG. Unfortunately, the risk of infection and the
222 need to undergo surgery are also significant limitations in this case [1].

223 3. Application Areas of Artificial Intelligence

224 This review focuses on five main application areas where AI- and ML-based algorithms
225 have been used within BCI systems so far. The application of AI- and ML-based algorithms
226 within individual areas is discussed in detail in the following subsections. Fig. 3 illustrates
227 the areas where the AI and ML were used in the past marked by the red frame. The selected
228 application areas are as follows:

- 229 1. *Calibration* – The first area deals with the calibration of BCI equipment, which is
230 time consuming procedure but significantly affects the subsequent accuracy of the
231 entire measurement. Therefore, various approaches to streamline [60, 61, 62, 63, 64]
232 or completely eliminate the calibration process [18, 65, 66, 67] while maintaining BCI
233 accuracy have been mentioned.
- 234 2. *Noise Suppression* – The second area has been dedicated to noise suppression, espe-
235 cially in EEG-based BCIs [68, 69, 19].
- 236 3. *Communication* – This application domain focused on one of the most common prac-
237 tical tasks used in BCI systems involving character recognition [70, 71, 72, 73, 74] or
238 computer cursor control [20, 75, 76].
- 239 4. *Mental Condition Estimation* – This area focused on the estimation of mental condi-
240 tion, such as mental workload classification [77, 32, 78, 79], stress level detection [79],

Figure 3: A schematic illustration of individual steps for obtaining, processing and classifying the brain signals using non-invasive EEG, fNIRS, MEG, fMRI and invasive iCor, ECoG signals. The five main application areas addressed in this review are in bold. Red frames indicate domains where the AI and ML were already used.

241 memory load estimation [80], fatigue detection in drivers [81, 82], emotion estimation
 242 [83, 32, 84, 21, 85], awareness [86] or wakeful and sleep states detection [87].

243 5. *Motor Imagery* – The last, most represented area, involved the classification of brain
 244 signals within MI tasks, where the user imagined the movement of one of the limbs
 245 [88, 89, 90, 91, 92] or the different types of movements [93, 94, 95, 2], that the classifier
 246 had to distinguish. An interesting part of this area was the use of AI- and ML-based
 247 algorithms for robot [96, 97, 98] or robot arm control [99, 100], exoskeleton control
 248 [101, 102, 103], wheelchair [22, 104] and vehicle control [105].

249 3.1. BCI Calibration

250 To ensure the reliable operation of BCIs, calibration of the device for a specific user
 251 is needed before its use. The user usually performs specific tasks in which the training
 252 data is obtained and used in the test phase to predict the output. Unfortunately, this is a
 253 time-consuming operation that also requires a large amount of data to be stored for each
 254 user [67]. In addition, for some patients suffering from, e.g. amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
 255 (ALS) or brainstem stroke, it can be difficult to remain alert and actively participate in

256 long calibration process [60]. This procedure usually takes 20 – 30 minutes and finding a
257 faster solution is therefore highly desirable [18]. Therefore, some authors have focused on
258 the implementation of AI and ML to ensure rapid calibration [60, 61, 62], auto-calibration
259 [63], self-recalibration [64] or complete elimination of the need for subject-specific calibration
260 [18, 65, 66, 67] (see summary in Table 1):

261 • **Convolutional Neural Network** – Convolutional neural network (CNN) is a deep,
262 forward, multi-layer network that uses convolution instead of general matrix multi-
263 plication in at least one of its layers. The network architecture consists of an input
264 layer, several hidden layers (convolutional, activation, pooling, fully-connected and
265 normalization layers) and an output layer. The advantage of CNN over a conventional
266 artificial neural network (ANN) lies in the ability to automatically detect and extract
267 a large number of signal features without the human supervision [106].

268 To create a subject-independent EEG-BCI, CNN was used in 2020 by Kwon et al.
269 [18]. The authors first created an extensive database containing records of 54 subjects
270 who performed left- and right-hand MIs over two days. A total of 21,600 MI tasks
271 trials have been recorded. Using this dataset and spectral-spatial input generation,
272 a representation of general brain signal patterns was created. In addition, a fusion
273 process that combined spectral-spatial inputs from different frequency domains was
274 incorporated into this approach. CNN with three convolutional layers, a concatenation
275 layer for fusion, and a fully connected layer was used to learn this representation
276 and the left- or right-hand MI classification. The classification accuracy (ACC) of
277 this subject-independent model with a value of 74.15% exceeded the accuracy of the
278 subject-dependent model (ACC = 71.32%). In order to improve the performance of
279 the algorithm, it would be appropriate to use the most discriminant features (e.g.
280 a frequency-by-time matrix). A similar result (ACC = 73.00%), using the separated
281 channel CNN, was obtained by Zhu et al. [65], who used the common spatial pattern for
282 feature extraction. However, testing on a small number of subjects was the limitation
283 of this approach.

284 Lee et al. [66] chose the CNN method to provide a zero-training P300 speller BCI
285 system because of its robustness to noise, the ability to distinguish neurophysiological
286 features and to subsequently generalize the relatively common features. Data from
287 55 healthy subjects who completed the conventional P300 speller paradigm, during
288 which they focused on a specific set of letters, were used to train the network (a total
289 of 99,000 training samples were generated). The accuracy of the algorithm in the
290 zero-training process with the value of ACC = 85.00% exceeded the accuracy of the
291 process with calibration (ACC = 82.00%). At the same time, it was proved that the
292 performance of the algorithm increased with a higher number of training samples used
293 (both in terms of data volume and diversity). The fact that the use of not all types
294 of data led to a more accurate classification was an interesting finding. The data with
295 low average signal amplitude, on the other hand, slightly impaired the classification
296 accuracy. The same approach for creating a subject-independent P300 BCI speller

297 was also chosen by Gao et al. [67], who achieved an average accuracy of only 75.34%
298 in online testing with the participation of 200 subjects.

- 299 • **Transfer Learning** – The ML-based transfer learning (TL) technique builds on stor-
300 ing and transferring knowledge from previously learned problem to a new similar prob-
301 lem. The more the current problem is related to the previous one, the easier it is to
302 transfer knowledge and learn this new issue. The use of a pre-trained model leads to a
303 reduction in time, resources and amount of labelled data required to train new models
304 [107].

305 According to Wu [61], it was very difficult to design an EEG-based BCI generic classi-
306 fier for rapid calibration due to the different neural responses of individual subjects to
307 the same stimuli. Therefore, to reduce the calibration time, weighted adaptation reg-
308 ularization with source domain selection (WARSDS) combining TL and regularization
309 was proposed. Use of the methods led to a minimization of the amount of labelled
310 subject-specific EEG data used, and thus to a reduction in the calibration time. The
311 application of the regularization method allowed the creation of a robust model even
312 when the set of training data was small. The implementation of TL led to an effective
313 use of relevant information from training data with new subjects. When tested on 18
314 subjects during the two-class image stimuli task, the computational cost was reduced
315 by 50%.

316 The TL-based approach also proved to be suitable for creating a completely calibration-
317 free EEG-BCI system used for imagined speech (the subject imagined pronouncing
318 a word without making sounds or articulating), as shown by Garcia-Salinas et al.
319 [108]. By implementing TL, it was possible to extend the created model to a new
320 subject, i.e. to optimize the model using combined data of multiple users. When
321 tested on 27 subjects, the calibration-free system using TL achieved lower accuracy
322 ($ACC = 65.65\%$) compared to the system that was calibrated ($ACC = 68.90\%$), but
323 this difference was not statistically significant.

- 324 • **Linear Discriminant Analysis** – Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) is one of the
325 basic supervised classifiers that can be used for classification into two or more classes.
326 The fact that the individual features are linearly separable is a prerequisite for the use
327 of LDA. The principle of this method is based on projecting data into the space of a
328 lower dimension while preserving important information. First, the distance between
329 the averages of the different classes is calculated, and then the distance between the
330 average and the sample of each class is computed. Finally, a lower dimensional space is
331 created, which maximizes the variance between the classes and minimizes the variance
332 within the class, thus achieving maximum discrimination [109].

333 To reduce the calibration time, weighted LDA (WLDA) was implemented as part of
334 a generic model set and combined model matching approach proposed by Jin et al.
335 [62]. First, signal features were extracted from EEG signals obtained from subjects
336 performing spelling tasks. These were clustered using k-means and a generic model

337 was created including those models trained by WLDA. Due to the great data diversity,
338 a matching model was generated. This model was able to assign the characteristics
339 obtained from the training dataset to those obtained from the data in the testing
340 phase. The resulting calibration time was reduced by 70.70%. It also turned out that
341 not all generic models were suitable for every participant. Improperly chosen model
342 led to low classification accuracy ($ACC = 43.30\%$).

343 An auto-calibrating and online co-adaptive BCI system that continuously adapted the
344 LDA-based classification model was reported by Faller et al. [63]. This technique
345 did not require any BCI expert interaction and feedback was provided online in less
346 than five minutes. The study included 24 users with severe disabilities – tetraparesis,
347 tetraplegia or locked-in state (LIS) performing two-class MI (right and left hand MI).
348 According to the authors, it is also necessary to verify the functionality of subjects in
349 a minimally conscious state.

350 Unfortunately, non-stationary brain signals can lead to reduced decoding stability
351 during BCI use, which requires recalibration of BCI systems. In order not to have to
352 interrupt the use of the device and recalibrate it for a long time, Jarosiewicz et al.
353 [64] designed self-recalibration using data obtained during the practical use of BCI.
354 Testing of the method was conducted on one subject with ALS performing cursor
355 control tasks who had 96-channel iCor silicon microelectrode arrays implanted. First,
356 a conventional calibration of the subject’s brain activity mapping system was performed.
357 The nerve activity was converted into cursor movements using the Kalman filter (KF)
358 and intended cursor clicks were decoded using LDA. Based on the data obtained during
359 the measurements, the decoders were recalibrated at regular intervals. The user could
360 thus use the BCI without the need to perform daily calibration tasks across 11 research
361 sessions spanning 29 days without degrading the quality of the cursor control. However,
362 testing on a larger number of subjects is necessary.

- 363 • **Gaussian Process Regression** – The Gaussian process regression (GPR) method
364 is one of the most powerful supervised ML-based techniques. GPR is based on the
365 Bayesian nonparametric approach to regression and can be used effectively to solve
366 problems, even in cases where a small dataset is available. This approach allows
367 making predictions using prior knowledge and providing measures of uncertainty over
368 predictions [110].

369 Brandman et al. [60] proposed a three-minute rapid calibration for iCor-based BCI.
370 Data of three patients with two 96-channel iCor silicon microelectrode arrays perform-
371 ing cursor control were used for testing. For rapid neural decoding, GPR with the
372 discriminative KF (DKF) was used in the calibration phase and closed-loop control
373 was used instead of the open-loop imagery step. Updating the decoder parameters
374 every 2 – 5 seconds instead of 2 – 5 minutes also reduced the calibration time. In
375 addition, the calibration steps were automated so that no personnel intervention was
376 required. Although the authors stated that BCI systems could be used without any
377 participant learning or lengthy calibration, this statement was based on the results of

378 experiments performed on a very small number of subjects.

379 • **Hierarchical Cluster Analysis** – The unsupervised learning approach to hierarchi-
380 cal cluster analysis (HCA) is used to sort units into groups (clusters) so that units
381 belonging to the same group were more similar than objects from other groups. The
382 clusters can be created based on two approaches. The first one is divisive (dividing
383 one cluster into several smaller clusters) while the other one is agglomerative (join-
384 ing individual objects into clusters). The graphical representation of HCA is called a
385 dendogram [111].

386 Wei et al. [112] implemented HCA to create an EEG-BCI system that reduced the
387 calibration time for a new user by 90.00% (from 18 minutes to 1.72 minutes) without
388 compromising the decoding accuracy. They proposed to use HCA to evaluate the inter-
389 and intra-subject variability of EEG calibration data measured during the simulated
390 driving task and verified the possibilities of drowsiness-detection transfer between other
391 subjects and a new user. The need for a large amount of data to learn the model is
392 considered as the method's main disadvantage.

Table 1: Overview of AI-based algorithms and their use for calibration.

Author, source	Technique	Algorithm	Type of calibration	Data/Dataset	Result
Kwon et al. [18]	EEG	CNN	calibration-free	54 healthy subjects	ACC = 74.15%
Zhu et al. [65]	EEG	CNN	calibration-free	25 subjects and BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset	ACC = 73.00%
Lee et al. [66]	EEG	CNN	calibration-free	55 healthy subjects	ACC = 85.00%
Gao et al. [67]	EEG	CNN	calibration-free	200 healthy subjects	ACC = 75.34%
Wu [61]	EEG	wARSDS	rapid calibration	18 subjects	–
Garcia-Salinas et al. [108]	EEG	TL	calibration-free	27 subjects	ACC = 65.65%
Jin et al. [62]	EEG	k-means-WLDA	rapid calibration	12 healthy subjects	ACC = 80.00%
Faller et al. [63]	EEG	LDA	auto-calibration	22 subjects with motor impairment	ACC = 68.60%
Jarosiewicz et al. [64]	iCor	KF-LDA	self-recalibration	1 subject with ALS	–
Brandman et al. [60]	iCor	GPR-DKF	rapid calibration	3 subjects with tetraplegia	–
Wei et al. [112]	EEG	HCA	rapid calibration	37 healthy subjects	–

BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset [113] – EEG from 9 subjects performing 2-classes MI (right hand, left hand)

393 3.2. Noise Suppression

394 To obtain and analyze the important information from the measured signals, the brain
395 signals must be of high-quality, ideally free of all interference. The biggest challenge in
396 eliminating the interference lies in EEG signals, which are prone to noise due to their low
397 amplitudes. In addition, the SNR value of EEG is also very low, as useful signals are often
398 contaminated with physiological artifacts (movement and muscle artifacts, cardiac activity,
399 or the most common eye blinking/movements) that have a wide spectral and variable to-
400 pographical distribution [68, 15]. Therefore, the use of AI- and ML-based algorithms is the
401 most widespread in this measurement technique. Although, in the past, there were a number
402 of studies [114, 115, 116, 117, 118], which used AI-based and ML-based algorithms to elim-
403 inate interference in conventional brain signal measurements. However, their application in
404 the field of automated processing of continuous BCI signals may not be as effective.

405 For these reasons, this subsection includes only studies in which signals recorded using
406 a BCI device were used for testing [68, 69, 19] or the authors identified them as suitable for
407 the use in BCI applications [119, 120, 121, 122], as summarized in Table 2.

- 408 • **Artificial Neural Network** – The classic forward ANN consists of an input layer,
409 one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Each layer consists of neurons that
410 transmit signals and transform them using transfer functions. The signal propagates
411 only in the forward direction, i.e. from the input layer towards the output one. The
412 principle of ANN’s activity is inspired by the behaviour of biological neurons in the
413 brain, which allows ANN to learn and adapt to time-varying and nonlinear features
414 [123].

415 An automated algorithm combining ANN with independent component analysis (ICA)
416 to remove EEG artifacts was reported by Radüntz et al. [120] in 2017. Prior to the
417 classification using ANN, top-plot images and power spectra of ICA components were
418 created, which served as inputs for feature generation and the subsequent classifica-
419 tion. Then, the artifact components were removed and the EEG components were
420 reconstructed, leading to the acquisition of an artifact-free EEG signal. The method
421 was tested on 57 subjects and $ACC = 95.84\%$ was achieved, which was a slightly bet-
422 ter result compared to the use of support vector machines (SVM) in the classification
423 phase ($ACC = 94.04\%$). The results of the classification using algorithms were com-
424 pared with the results of the classification performed by human experts. The ANN
425 method matched on average in 89.47% of cases, while, for SVM, the average match
426 value was 84.34%. The fact that it was not limited to a specific type of artifact was the
427 advantage of the ICA-ANN. The disadvantages of the method included the need for a
428 large amount of data for learning, finding the optimal setting of network parameters
429 and time-consuming.

430 In combination with the wavelet transform (WT), ANN has also been shown to be
431 effective in eliminating motion artifacts (MA) in fNIRS signals, as demonstrated by Lee
432 et al. [124]. The most contaminated signals were first identified using entropy. These
433 were then decomposed into a time-frequency representation using the WT method

434 (*Daubechies6* mother wavelet and ten levels of decomposition). Wavelet sub-bands
435 were used as inputs to ANN. The ANN contained six hidden layers with more than 400
436 neurons while the output layer comprised one neuron. The network was trained using a
437 back-propagation (BP) algorithm. Six subjects moving on the ground or on a treadmill
438 were used for testing. The effectiveness of the method was evaluated according to the
439 contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR) and reached a value of 0.73. The authors stated that a
440 significant disadvantage of the method consisted in its dependence on the quality of
441 input signals and the need to find the optimal ANN setting in order to achieve good
442 results.xs

- 443 • **Autoencoder** – The autoencoder (AE) is a forward multilayer network with a sym-
444 metrical architecture containing an encoder encoding the input into a compressed
445 representation (code) and a decoder decoding it and reconstructing the original input.
446 It is an unsupervised feature learning algorithm that seeks to find a better feature
447 representation of the input high-dimensional data. AE can contain only three lay-
448 ers (input, hidden and output), but also several dozen hidden layers forming a deep
449 network [125].

450 A specific type of AE, so-called stacked sparse AE (SSAE), was used by Yang et al. [68]
451 to filter ocular artifacts from EEG signals. SSAE is a network containing several layers
452 of basic SAE, which applies sparsity value during the training phase (it helps to extract
453 more relevant features). Three hidden layers were used for each SAE. The method was
454 tested on four subjects and reached an average accuracy of 75.10%. The advantages of
455 the proposed method were summarized as follows: there was no need for simultaneous
456 scanning of the reference in the form of electrooculographic signal (EOG); the method
457 was also suitable for systems with a small number of measuring electrodes, low time
458 complexity and high generalization capability. The need to perform a large number of
459 experiments to ensure the optimal setting of parameters affecting the reconstructive
460 capability of the method was a disadvantage of the algorithm.

- 461 • **Convolutional Neural Network** – The CNN-based approach has also been used in
462 the field of suppressing the unwanted interference in EEG recording, as shown in a
463 study by Mathe et al. [121]. They used it for automated removal of EOG, electrocar-
464 diographic (ECG) and electromyographic (EMG) artifacts. Since the main limitations
465 of the CNN include a relatively demanding setting of optimal hyperparameters values,
466 in this case, a spider monkey-based electric fish optimizer (SM-EFO) was employed for
467 their optimization. The algorithm was tested on real recordings from the CHB-MIT
468 Scalp EEG Database [126], which were loaded with EOG, ECG and EMG artifacts.
469 The performance of the algorithm was evaluated using the root mean square error
470 (RMSE) parameter, whose average value was 0.015. Unfortunately, the optimal pa-
471 rameter settings and network efficiency were obtained at the expense of computational
472 complexity. According to the authors, a further improvement in accuracy could be
473 achieved by providing an additional network block.

- 474 • **Recurrent Quantum Neural Network** – The connection between quantum me-

475 chanics and ANN theory is called the recurrent quantum neural network (RQNN).
476 It is a recurrent type of network with one hidden layer containing so-called quantum
477 neurons based on the superposition of a quantum state. The dynamics of individ-
478 ual neurons are thus ignored in this case and the average behaviour of all neurons is
479 modelled using the quantum activation function (Schrödinger wave equation) [69].

480 Ganhi et al. [69] used RQNN to remove the interference contained in EEG signals
481 because the algorithm did not require any information about the nature of the noise.
482 The RQNN method was able to capture the statistical behaviour of the input signal and
483 estimate the useful signal. Raw EEG signals were first scaled in the range of 0 to 2 and
484 then, sample by sample, they entered the RQNN, which extracted the enhanced signals.
485 The verification of the accuracy of the method was performed on real recordings. The
486 relatively low accuracy of the algorithm ($ACC = 66.59\%$) could be attributed to the
487 method of selecting network parameters. These were selected heuristically and using
488 the two-step inner-outer fivefold cross-validation method. The authors stated that,
489 in the future experiments, it would be appropriate to select parameter values using
490 some optimization methods, such as particle swarm optimization (PSO) or genetic
491 algorithm (GA).

- 492 • **Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System** – The combined adaptive neuro-fuzzy
493 inference system (ANFIS) is based on a combination of forward ANN and the Takagi-
494 Sugeno fuzzy inference system. The combination of these two techniques means that
495 ANFIS can work with inaccurate data and learn from the environment. The network
496 architecture contains a total of five layers (an adaptive input layer, a non-adaptive
497 rule layer, a non-adaptive normalizing layer, an adaptive defuzzification layer, and a
498 non-adaptive summary layer) [127].

499 In order for the ANFIS method to work effectively, it is essential to set its parameters
500 appropriately: the number of epochs, the number of fuzzy rules, the number of linear
501 and nonlinear parameters, and the type of membership function. In a study published
502 by Sunny et al. in 2021 [19], the following settings proved promising for filtering EEG
503 signals: 1,000 epochs, 16 fuzzy rules, 80 linear and 24 non-linear parameters, and a
504 bell-shaped membership function. Since the output signal extracted by ANFIS was
505 often distorted by high-frequency noise, this signal was filtered by the Hilbert-Huang
506 transform (HHT) method, which removed this interference and improved the quality
507 of the extracted EEG signals. Effective removal of EOG, ECG, and EMG artifacts
508 resulted in a high average accuracy of the method ($ACC = 99.06\%$), but at the expense
509 of long training time.

- 510 • **Support Vector Machines** – The principle of supervised learning SVM classifier
511 is based on the construction of a hyperplane so that the data belonging to mutually
512 different classes lie in opposite half-spaces. Ideally, the minimum value of the distances
513 of the points from the hyperplane should be as large as possible (there should be the
514 widest possible band without points on both sides of the hyperplane). The points that
515 lie at the edge of this band are then called support vectors [128].

516 To classify the artifacts contained in continuously measured EEG signals, the SVM
517 algorithm was implemented by Lawhern et al. [129]. Autoregressive (AR) models were
518 used for feature extraction; they were able to obtain scale-independent signal features.
519 Such a model could then be used for a wide range of different signals and subjects.
520 Subsequently, SVM was applied for the final classification of EEG artifacts. When
521 tested on seven subjects, the authors achieved $ACC = 95.86\%$. The disadvantage of
522 the method included the simultaneous sensing of the EOG signal and the need for a
523 large amount of data for training the classifier.

524 An interesting hybrid approach was also chosen by Sai et al. [119], who combined
525 SVM with WT and ICA methods. The input signals were first decomposed by WT
526 (*Daubechies8* mother wavelet and eight levels of decomposition) for preliminary filter-
527 ing. Subsequently, these signals entered the ICA algorithm and were decomposed into
528 individual components. The pre-trained SVM was used to classify the ICA compo-
529 nents into ocular artifacts and a useful EEG signal. The advantage of the algorithm
530 consisted, in addition to high $ACC = 99.01\%$, in automation of the entire process,
531 and, thus, suitability for BCI system. Moreover, the resulting signal was not dis-
532 torted. However, testing the effectiveness of the algorithm for other types of artifacts
533 is needed. A very similar automated approach was also proposed by Yasoda et al.
534 [122], who combined WT (*Daubechies4* mother wavelet was used), ICA and fuzzy
535 kernel SVM (FKSVM) methods. In this case, lower accuracy was achieved ($ACC =$
536 86.10%), but, in addition to ocular artifacts, MAs and electrical power shift (EPS)
537 were also removed. The need to have a large amount of data available for model
538 training can be considered a limitation.

- 539 • **K-Nearest Neighbors** – The k-nearest neighbours (KNN) supervised learning tech-
540 nique is used to classify objects into two or more classes. In the learning phase, all
541 objects of the training set are distributed in an N -dimensional space. During testing
542 phase, the test object is placed in the same space and the distances with all training
543 objects are calculated. The test object is assigned to a class where most of the k
544 nearest training objects belong [130].

545 Gao et al. [131] proposed a real-time algorithm for removing EOG artifacts, which
546 was based on a combination of ICA, principal component analysis (PCA) and KNN.
547 The input EEG signals were decomposed into individual ICA components, and signal
548 features were extracted from them. Topography and power spectral density features
549 were used, as they are very characteristic of EOG artifacts and are often used in the
550 visual evaluation of EEG. To reduce the dimension, the PCA method was applied
551 and, finally, the low-dimensional features were introduced into the KNN classifier to
552 identify EOG artifacts. When tested on 16 subjects, the combined approach reached
553 $ACC = 99.79\%$. In addition, the effectiveness of the method was verified during online
554 measurements using the BCI2000 environment, where it was able to filter out EOG
555 and extract a high-quality EEG signal. The need for simultaneous sensing of the EOG
556 signal was the disadvantage of the approach.

- 557 • **K-Means** – The unsupervised learning clustering k-means technique is based on the
558 inclusion of objects in the cluster to the centre of gravity (centroid) of which the objects
559 are closest. The initial placement of the centroids is usually random. The objects are
560 assigned to the nearest centroids and form clusters. The algorithm proceeds iteratively
561 and recalculates the positions of the centroids so that it is the centre of gravity of
562 the cluster of objects belonging to it. The objects are again assigned to the newly
563 determined centroids, and this process is repeated until the position of the centroids
564 stabilizes [132].

565 In a study published by Maddirala et al. [133] in 2021, a combination of k-means
566 and singular spectrum analysis (SSA) was used to eliminate eye-blink artifacts. The
567 input EEG signal was first decomposed into individual source components using time-
568 domain signal features and the k-mean clustering algorithm. The fractal dimension
569 was calculated for individual components (eye-blink artifact was a slow varying com-
570 ponent, and thus a lower value of fractal dimension was assumed). Eye-blink artifact
571 components were processed by SSA and subtracted from the EEG signal, resulting
572 in the extraction of pure EEG. According to relative RMSE (RRMSE), an average
573 value of 13.47% was achieved without any change in the character of the EEG signal.
574 However, the performance of the algorithm was strongly dependent on the appropri-
575 ate choice of the threshold of fractal dimension to distinguish the useful signal and
576 artifacts.

- 577 • **Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm** – The meta-heuristic artificial bee colony algo-
578 rithm (ABC), like most nature-inspired techniques, was designed to solve nonlinear
579 problems and is used mainly in solving optimization problems. To find the optimal
580 solution or a solution close to the optimal one, these nature-inspired optimization tech-
581 niques use an iterative process and intelligent learning strategies for the exploration
582 and exploitation of the search space [134]. Specifically, the ABC algorithm was in-
583 spired by the intelligent foraging behaviour of the honey bee swarm. The principle is
584 based on the search for food sources, and, from all the sources found, the one with the
585 higher quality (fitness value) has a better chance of being selected [135].

586 The ABC algorithm was used to calculate the optimal weights of adaptive noise can-
587 celler (ANC), which was used for EEG filtering by Ahirwal et al. [136]. Optimal
588 weights were determined by minimizing the mean square error (MSE). EEG data
589 measured by the BCI 2000 system, which were interfered with white Gaussian noise
590 (WGN) and subsequently filtered, were used for testing. The filtration result was
591 evaluated using a correlation coefficient (r). The results showed a significant average
592 correlation ($r = 0.90$) between the original and filtered EEG signals. Moreover, the
593 adaptation time of the algorithm was very low. However, the good performance of the
594 algorithm was highly dependent on the appropriate setting of the ABC algorithm.

- 595 • **Particle Swarm Optimization** – The principle of the nature-inspired PSO technique
596 is based on the behaviour of a flock of birds in search of food. The individual particles
597 move in the search space and are defined by their position, speed and memory of

598 previous search successes. Their positions and speeds are iteratively updated both on
599 the basis of their own experience and on the basis of the experience of more successful
600 particles [137].

601 Inertia-weighted PSO was used to find the optimal values of the ANC filter weights by
602 Ahirwal et al. [138]. EEG-BCI signals were contaminated with WGN and subsequently
603 filtered by hybrid ANC-PSO. A high correlation ($r = 0.95$) was achieved between the
604 original and the filtered signal, and the PSO was thus able to surpass GA and ABC
605 algorithms. However, the greater computational cost of PSO can be considered a
606 disadvantage.

607 • **Marine Predators Algorithm** – In the field of EEG signal processing, relatively new
608 algorithms can also emerge, such as the marine predators algorithm (MPA) introduced
609 in 2020. The MPA method is based on the rules of the optimal strategy of foraging
610 and meeting prey and predator in marine ecosystems. The algorithm is based on the
611 so-called "*survival of the fittest*" theory, where predators must choose the optimal
612 strategy to maximize the number of encounters with prey [139].

613 Yadav et al. [140] used this algorithm to optimize the ANC. The filter weights were
614 set by means of minimizing the error fitness function–MSE. Setting the population
615 size to 25 and the number of iterations to 1000 for the MPA algorithm turned out
616 to be the most suitable. When testing on data measured by EEG-BCI and loaded
617 with WGN, $r = 0.99$ was achieved. However, verification of the effectiveness of this
618 approach on artifacts typically found in EEG signals, such as EOG or EMG, is needed.
619 The need to find a suitable setting of the parameters of the MPA algorithm and higher
620 computational complexity may be a certain disadvantage of the method.

Table 2: Overview of AI-based algorithms and their use for noise suppression.

Author, source	Technique	Algorithm	Type of artifacts	Data/Dataset	Result
Radüntz et al. [120]	EEG	ICA-ANN ICA-SVM	not specified	57 subjects	ACC = 95.84% ACC = 94.04%
Lee et al. [124]	fNIRS	WT-ANN	MAs	6 walking subjects (2 with brain stroke and 4 healthy)	CNR = 0.73%
Yang et al. [68]	EEG	SSAE	EOG	BCI Competition IV-1 Dataset	ACC = 75.10%
Mathe et al. [121]	EEG	CNN-SM-EFO	EOG, ECG, EMG	CHB-MIT Scalp EEG Database	RMSE = 0.015
Gandhi et al. [69]	EEG	RQNN	not specified	BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset	ACC = 66.59%
Sunny et al. [19]	EEG	ANFIS-HHT	EOG, ECG, EMG	14 healthy subjects and BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset	ACC = 99.06%
Lawhern et al. [129]	EEG	AR-SVM	EOG, EMG, MAs	7 subjects	ACC = 95.86%
Sai et al. [119]	EEG	WT-ICA-SVM	EOG	11 healthy subjects	ACC = 99.01%
Yasoda et al. [122]	EEG	WT-ICA-FKSVM	EOG, MAs, EPS	not specified	ACC = 86.10%
Gao et al. [131]	EEG	ICA-PCA-KNN	EOG	16 healthy subjects	ACC = 99.79%
Maddirala et al. [133]	EEG	k-means-SSA	EOG	simulated dataset and 12 subjects	RRMSE = 13.47%
Ahirwal et al. [136]	EEG	ANC-ABC	WGN	EEG Motor Movement/Imagery Dataset	$r = 0.90$
Ahirwal et al. [138]	EEG	ANC-PSO	WGN	EEG Motor Movement/Imagery Dataset	$r = 0.95$
Yadav et al. [140]	EEG	ANC-MPA	WGN	EEG Motor Movement/Imagery Dataset	$r = 0.99$

BCI Competition IV-1 Dataset [113] – EEG from 7 healthy subjects performing 2-classes MI (selected from 3 classes: left hand, right hand, and foot)

BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset [113] – EEG from 9 subjects performing 2-classes MI (right hand, left hand)

CHB-MIT Scalp EEG Database [126] – EEG from 22 pediatric subjects with intractable seizures

EEG Motor Movement/Imagery Dataset [141] – EEG from 109 subjects performing 14 MI tasks

3.3. Use of BCI Systems for Communication Purposes

The provision of spelling and communication assistance to people with disabilities (e.g. patients with ALS, stroke, spinal cord injury, etc.) is an important area in which BCIs are widely used. The modern BCI system allows these people to communicate and restore their social life through brain signals without the need for any muscle motion [142, 143]. AI- and ML-based methods are most often used for character recognition in BCI communication systems, wherein two main paradigms can be encountered.

The first one is based on the measurement of event-related potentials (ERPs), which manifest themselves in brain signals as a positive deflection after a specific event occurs. This technique is known as the oddball paradigm [142, 144]. This approach is used, for example, by the P300 BCI speller device [70, 71, 72, 73, 74], whose row or column filled with 36 characters randomly intensifies for 140 ms every 200 ms, or the N200 BCI speller device [145] based on visual motion stimuli (a row or column of vertical bars in rectangle under characters appear and move leftward for 140 ms every 200 ms). The user's task was to focus on the character to be selected and to ignore the others. The second approach is based on the measurement of steady-state visual evoked potentials (SSVEPs) [146], which manifest themselves in brain signals as positive and negative fluctuations. The stimulus flashes on the screen with a certain constant frequency, which leads to the induction of SSVEP with the same frequency and higher harmonics as with the stimulus [142]. In addition to the character recognition, AI- and ML-based algorithms are used to classify the signals measured during the control of a BCI computer cursor [20, 75, 76], see the summary of the results in Table 3.

- **Convolutional Neural Network** – CNN was used by Cecotti et al. [70] for the classification of P300 speller waves. In conducting the experiments, the authors tested several scenarios (different number of classifiers, different number of training databases, etc.). CNN containing five classifiers, each of which was trained on a different database, proved to be the most suitable variant achieving an accuracy of 95.50% in characters recognition. The number of epochs (number of times a row/column has to flash on one character) was 15 in this case, which was the maximum number performed in this protocol. The experiments were conducted on only two subjects and further verification on a larger number of participants is needed to obtain more reliable results.

Nguyen et al. [146] performed a similar experiment for characters recognition, using an SSVEP-based speller containing a 58-character virtual keyboard, on a large number of participants, a total of eight subjects without visual impairment. During online testing, CNN achieved an accuracy of 97.37% in the classification of SSVEP signals using only a single dry-electrode. The disadvantage of the single-channel approach lies in the longer training time (500 epochs) for obtaining optimized CNN compared to the multichannel method, in which only ten epochs were sufficient.

- **Long Short Term Memory** – The recurrent long short term memory (LSTM) network excels especially in the ability to learn long-term dependencies and store this information in memory for a long time. The network architecture consists of a sequence of repeating modules of ANNs. Each module contains elements corresponding

662 to four ANN layers that work together. Each LSTM unit contains an input and an
663 output gate, a forget gate and a cell. The cell remembers values at time intervals and
664 the gates decide which information will be forgotten and which will be remembered
665 [147].

666 LSTM was implemented by Olsen et al. [20] as part of the architecture for the control
667 of a BCI computer cursor, which allowed typing on a virtual keyboard. To improve
668 the cursor control trajectories, a prediction model that modelled long-term and short-
669 term dependencies was created. The short-term dependencies (movements towards
670 some targets and away from others affect the future cursor movements) were modelled
671 using the potential field while the long-term dependencies (user activity during the last
672 few dozen attempts has an impact on its future activity) were modelled using LSTM.
673 Three LSTMs each containing 512 hidden units and 1000 training epochs were used.
674 During testing on nine subjects, an accuracy of 58.00% and 75.00% was achieved in
675 predicting the character when it was early (first four characters) and late (fifth and
676 later characters) in word, respectively. Since no rigorous optimization of the hyperpa-
677 rameters was conducted, further improvement could be achieved by incorporating an
678 optimization algorithm.

- 679 • **Linear Discriminant Analysis** – An interesting approach was proposed by Schreuder
680 et al. [148], who performed experiments on a subject with a brainstem ischemic stroke.
681 The purpose of the experiments was to use ERP-based BCI to control the photo ap-
682 plication. The photo application worked on a similar principle as the P300 speller, but
683 the characters were exchanged with photos. This type of application was intended for
684 browsing, viewing and sharing photos via the Internet. An LDA classifier was used to
685 classify the signal features, which were regularized using shrinkage regularization of the
686 covariance matrix to prevent over-fitting. The test results were promising, however, a
687 larger sample of subjects is needed.

688 An extended variant of the LDA method, the so-called stepwise LDA (SLDA), was
689 used to classify the EEG signal features obtained using the P300 speller in a study
690 by Oralhan [71]. He also investigated whether the SLDA is able to achieve higher
691 classification accuracy when using only visual stimuli, audio stimuli, or a hybrid ap-
692 proach combining audio and visual stimuli. As expected by the author, when tested
693 on seven subjects, the combination of audio and visual stimuli achieved the highest
694 average accuracy, specifically 90.31%, followed by 78.06% when using only the visual
695 stimuli. The use of only the audio stimuli was the least effective (ACC = 54.08%).
696 Nevertheless, the tests were performed only on healthy subjects and it is, therefore,
697 necessary to verify the functionality also in patients with severe injuries.

698 Improvements in the accuracy of the P300 speller characters recognition were also
699 sought by Qu et al. [72], who used the Bayesian LDA (BLDA) algorithm. In addi-
700 tion, instead of conventional two-dimensional (2-D) stimuli, they chose an approach
701 based on three-dimensional (3-D) stereo visual stimuli. The use of the 3-D paradigm
702 was intended to evoke higher ERPs and improve classification performance. The ex-

703 experiments were performed on 12 subjects wearing 3-D glasses and 3-D flashing cubes
704 with characters were displayed to them in a 3-D screen mode. The results of the
705 study confirmed the hypothesis that, using 3-D stimuli, BLDA was able to achieve
706 higher accuracy (ACC = 94.00%) compared to using conventional 2-D stimuli (ACC
707 = 89.10%). However, realistic 3-D stimuli can be uncomfortable for some people and
708 may cause dizziness.

709 To improve the classification accuracy in ALS patients, Borgheai et al. [149] chose a
710 new visuo-mental (VM) paradigm combining classical visual tasks (oddball paradigm)
711 and mental arithmetic operations. According to their assumption, the incorporation of
712 mental operations should compensate for the patient's impairments in the visual tasks.
713 For the classification of hemodynamic features obtained during fNIRS measurements
714 in six patients with ALS, the LDA algorithm achieved an accuracy of 81.30%, i.e. the
715 results were better compared to the classification performed using EEG signals (ACC
716 = 74.00%), which were measured simultaneously with fNIRS. High variance in the
717 sensitivity due to the low number of targets and the limited number of characters to
718 be spelt, so that the measurement is not too tedious for the participants, were the
719 limitations of the study. To increase the accuracy of the classification, the authors
720 suggest the use of a classifier based on ANN.

721 According to the results of experiments reported by Bacher et al. [75], the LDA has also
722 been successful in classifying invasive iCor signals. These were recorded during cursor
723 control and an on-screen virtual keyboard in a patient with tetraplegia and anarthria
724 (caused by bilateral pontine infarction) who had a 96-channel microelectrode array
725 implanted. Although the method achieved a high accuracy (ACC = 91.85%), the
726 authors recommended increasing the performance and robustness of this approach in
727 further studies.

728 As BCI systems make mistakes in communication tasks, these mistakes then need to
729 be corrected by the user, which reduces BCI performance and can be frustrating for
730 many subjects, Even-Chen et al. [76] introduced an automatic error detect-and-undo
731 system. The system automatically detected whether the user identified an error and
732 automatically took corrective action. Here, the LDA functioned as a binary classifier
733 for predicting the trial's outcome (predicting whether the trial succeeded or failed).
734 Two subjects with a 96-channel iCor silicon microelectrode array were used for testing,
735 one with ALS and the other with a spinal cord injury performing cursor control. Target
736 selection outcomes were classified with an average accuracy of 77.45%. However, a
737 compromise had to be made between the longer classification latency and the accuracy
738 of the system.

- 739 • **Support Vector Machines** – According to Zhang et al. [145], the SVM method
740 can be used to classify minimally invasive ECoG-BCI signals. The signals in this
741 study were measured in five subjects with epilepsy who had an 8-, 16-, or 32-electrode
742 grid implanted. The participants used the N200 BCI speller device during the ex-
743 periments and focused on the visual motion stimuli. Only one ECoG channel and

744 features extracted from ERP signals were used for SVM linear kernel classification.
745 In the experiments, an accuracy of 75.48% was achieved, but a significant improve-
746 ment ($ACC = 84.22\%$) occurred when the classifiers were provided together with ERP
747 features in addition to high gamma response features. However, the ascertainment of
748 which brain region can provide the best signals for the subsequent classification and is,
749 therefore, the most suitable for the implementation of the sensing electrode should be
750 the subject of further research. This could not be verified due to the limited number
751 of participants and limited electrode coverage.

752 In addition to ECoG-based BCI, the SVM algorithm has proved to be successful in
753 MEG-based BCI, as shown by Kurmanaviciute et al. [150], who detected selective
754 auditory attention. Fifteen healthy subjects were used for the measurement by means
755 of the whole-scalp 306-channel Elekta Neuromag VectorView MEG system (Elekta
756 Oy/MEGIN, Helsinki, Finland). The participants' task was to distinguish between
757 relevant and irrelevant acoustic information. During the experiments, two acoustic
758 word streams were played to the subjects simultaneously; the word "Yes" was repeat-
759 edly played on the left side while the word "No" was played on the right side. The
760 participant was supposed to choose one word and focus on it. The goal of the linear
761 SVM was to predict which word the user focused on. The SVM reached an accuracy
762 of 93.00% during offline classification. According to the authors, in the online classifi-
763 cation, the SVM can be trained only on samples from the beginning of the recording,
764 which can reduce the accuracy of the classification if the brain responses change during
765 the measurement.

- 766 • **Random Forest** – The supervised learning classifier random forest (RF) consists
767 of a set of several (up to hundreds) decision trees. As the resulting class, the one
768 that is most often marked with individual trees is selected [151]. The structure of
769 each tree consists of nodes in which the decision-making process takes place and edges
770 that represent decision variants. The classification procedure starts at the root node,
771 continues through the internal nodes, and ends at the terminal nodes representing the
772 classes [152]. Its ability to process data containing errors or missing values is the main
773 advantage of the algorithm [151].

774 The RF classifier was implemented by Akram et al. [73] to improve the classification
775 accuracy of P300 speller character typing. In addition to accuracy, the proposed
776 approach also excelled at high speed, as the authors modified the classic P300 speller
777 paradigm by incorporating a text on the nine keys (T9) interface. The new approach
778 was tested on ten healthy subjects and this word suggestion mechanism led to an
779 average improvement of 51.87% when writing ten random words (from 3.47 min per
780 word to 1.67 min per word). Compared to the SVM classifier, RF achieved significantly
781 higher accuracy using fewer stimulus repetitions. However, the complexity and longer
782 RF training time must be taken into account.

- 783 • **Fuzzy Logic** – Fuzzy logic allows capturing the approximate reasoning that is typical
784 for human thinking and a real environment full of inaccuracies. This is due to the fact

785 that it is a multivalued logic, i.e. it works with all values in the interval of $\langle 0; 1 \rangle$,
786 not only with logical values of 0 and 1. The fuzzy model is based on fuzzy rules in the
787 form of *if-then* rules and the classification of the object into a class is represented by
788 the degree of truth [153].

789 A set of classifiers based on a combination of fuzzy logic and Choquet integrals, so-
790 called fuzzy integrals (FIs), has been successfully used to classify P300-based BCI
791 signals by Cavrini et al. [74]. When tested on five healthy subjects, a value of 0.61
792 was achieved according to the efficiency (EFF) parameter. In addition, the classifier
793 was able to recognize uncertain situations and refrain from classification in these cases
794 in order to avoid making the wrong decision, which led to an increase in the safety
795 of the equipment. However, the effectiveness of the classifier has not been verified in
796 online testing and in disabled subjects.

Table 3: Overview of AI-based algorithms and their use for communication.

Author, source	Technique	Algorithm	Task	Data/Dataset	Result
Cecotti et al. [70]	EEG	CNN	P300 speller characters recognition	BCI Competition III-2 Dataset	ACC = 95.50%
Nguyen et al. [146]	EEG	CNN	SSVEP speller characters recognition	8 healthy subjects	ACC = 97.37%
Olsen et al. [20]	EEG	CNN	control of a BCI computer cursor	9 subjects	ACC = 75.00%
Schreuder et al. [148]	EEG	LDA	ERP-BCI photo application control	1 subject with brain stroke	–
Oralhan [71]	EEG	SLDA	P300 speller characters recognition	7 healthy subjects	ACC = 90.31%
Qu et al. [72]	EEG	BLDA	P300 speller 3-D characters recognition	12 healthy subjects	ACC = 94.00%
Borgheai et al. [149]	fNIRS	LDA	VM speller characters recognition	6 subjects with ALS	ACC = 81.30%
Bacher et al. [75]	iCor	LDA	control of a BCI computer cursor	1 subject with infarction	ACC = 91.85%
Even-Chen et al. [76]	iCor	LDA	control of a BCI computer cursor	2 subjects with ALS and spinal cord injury	ACC = 77.45%
Zhang et al. [145]	ECoG	SVM	N200 speller characters recognition	5 subjects with epilepsy	ACC = 84.22%
Kurmanaviciute [150]	MEG	SVM	selective auditory attention	15 healthy subjects	ACC = 93.00%
Akram et al. [73]	EEG	RF	P300 speller characters recognition	10 healthy subjects	–
Cavrini et al. [74]	EEG	FIs	P300 speller characters recognition	5 healthy subjects	EFF = 0.61

BCI Competition III-2 Dataset [154] – EEG from 2 subjects focusing on characters ($[A - Z]$, $[1 - 9]$, and $[-]$) from matrix of size 6×6 characters

797 3.4. Mental Condition Estimation with the use of BCI Systems

798 Passive BCI systems sensing spontaneous brain activity without any special stimulus
799 presented to the participant have been used especially in the field of mental condition esti-
800 mation. For the purpose of optimizing the work environment and work performance, research
801 was conducted on mental workload classification [77, 32, 78, 79], stress-level detection [79]
802 or memory load estimation [80]. To prevent fatal accidents, passive BCI systems have also
803 been used for the early detection of driver fatigue [81, 82]. The use of BCI in patients with
804 disorder of consciousness (DOC), such as coma, vegetative state, minimally, etc., in whom
805 the level of consciousness cannot be estimated and their emotions adequately recognized is
806 also an important area [21, 86]. Therefore, a number of studies have focused on the auto-
807 matic estimation of emotions using brain signals [83, 32, 84, 21, 85] or awareness detection
808 [86]. As the sleep-wake cycle has been proved to affect epileptic activity, BCIs have been
809 used to estimate cognitive states, specifically wakeful and sleep states detection [87]. Details
810 of the use of AI- and ML-based algorithms in the field of mental condition estimation are
811 summarized in this subsection and in Table 4.

812 • **Artificial Neural Network** – For the purpose of optimizing the work environment,
813 Casson [77] implemented forward ANN with five hidden layers and BP training algo-
814 rithm. The classification task was focused on estimating whether the human operator
815 is in a state of high or low mental workload. The experiments were performed on
816 118 real publicly available EEG recordings obtained from eight subjects performing
817 tasks in a flight simulator, for which ANN achieved an accuracy of 72.57%. However,
818 ANN worked effectively in cases where there was a short time between the testing and
819 training phases. As the time lag between the training and testing phases increased,
820 the accuracy significantly reduced. To alleviate this limitation, further experiments
821 were reported in which WGN was intentionally added to raw EEG signals and ANN
822 was trained on these interfered signals. Although the average accuracy of the network
823 was lower (ACC = 65.45%) and the need to retrain the network was not completely
824 eliminated, the results were consistent, and, therefore, the author saw the potential
825 for further research.

826 • **Multilayer Perceptron** – A special type of multilayer forward ANN called multilayer
827 perceptron (MLP) is characterized by the fact that each neuron of the layer is con-
828 nected to all neurons in the previous layer. MLP uses a non-linear activation function,
829 and network training is based on a supervised learning BP technique [155].

830 Sanchez-Reolid et al. [83] compared several types of MLP architectures, of which the
831 best results (ACC = 85.00%) were obtained with three hidden layers containing 30, 8
832 and 3 neurons in the first, second and third layers, respectively. The Bayesian regu-
833 larization method was used for error minimization. The task of MLP was to correctly
834 estimate the emotional states of the subjects tested. During the experiments, 16 par-
835 ticipants were shown several sets of images selected from the *International Affective*
836 *Picture System (IAPS)* [156]. At the same time, EEG signals were recorded and the

837 participants' responses to the emotions triggered were recorded in the form of ques-
838 tionnaires. These were then compared with valence, arousal and dominance values,
839 which were previously known from IAPS and also served as target outputs for MLP.
840 The disadvantage consisted in the need for a large amount of data for MLP training,
841 which may not always be available.

- 842 • **Convolutional Neural Network** – The usefulness of CNN in both emotion estima-
843 tion and workload detection was investigated in experiments conducted by Appriou
844 et al. [32], where EEG data recorded from 22 participants coming from study the
845 study presented in [157] performing various tasks were used to evaluate the effective-
846 ness in detecting the workload (low or high). And for emotion (arousal and valence)
847 estimation, data from 32 participants from the *Database for Emotion Analysis using*
848 *Physiological Signals (DEAP)* [158] was employed. CNN performed significantly bet-
849 ter at detecting workload with an average value of $ACC = 68.23\%$, compared to an
850 estimate of emotions for which only $ACC = 45.51\%$ was achieved. When using CNN
851 classification, the use of subject-specific calibration, instead of subject-independent
852 calibration, was recommended. The need for a lot of training trials (up to several
853 hundred) was the limitation of CNN, so the use of data-sets with a low number of
854 training data was impossible. The same limitation was also noted by Gao et al. [82]
855 when using spatial-temporal CNN for driver fatigue detection. However, thanks to the
856 spatial-temporal structure, this type of network achieved a very accurate classification
857 with $ACC = 97.37\%$ when tested on eight subjects using a drive simulator during
858 wakefulness and fatigue.

859 CNN was also able to distinguish drowsy/non-drowsy states very accurately ($ACC =$
860 99.30%) using images recorded by the fNIRS technique, as shown by the results of a
861 study presented by Tanveer et al. [81]. A 28-channel continuous-wave fNIRS system
862 was used in 13 volunteers while operating the control simulator. CNN was used to
863 classify the colour maps created from each time window. The use of smaller windows
864 turned out to be more efficient compared to using larger windows. However, LSTM
865 ($ACC = 89.31\%$) proved to be a slightly superior algorithm for the CNN method,
866 which achieved an accuracy of 87.45% when detecting mental workload, according to
867 the results of experiments conducted by Asgher et al. [78]. Brain activity signals were
868 obtained from the prefrontal cortex of 15 healthy subjects using the fNIRS technique.
869 The better performance of LSTM was probably due to the fact that it included memory
870 units to better keep time-series patterns. The high computational complexity was the
871 disadvantage of both methods.

- 872 • **Autoencoder** – Jirayucharoensak et al. [84] proposed the use of stacked AE with a
873 hierarchical feature learning approach in combination with the PCA method for es-
874 timating emotions using EEG signals. The PCA method was used to find the most
875 important components from the power spectral density features. Subsequently, a co-
876 variate shift adaptation of principal components was performed to minimize the non-
877 stationarity of EEG signals. AE was used for the final classification of three levels

878 of valence and arousal states. The average accuracy reached only 52.74%, which was
879 mainly due to inter-subject variations between the EEG signals characteristics. It
880 has also been proved that, with the increasing number of nodes in the hidden layers,
881 the accuracy of the network has improved, but at the expense of computational time.
882 According to the authors, the solution could lie in incorporating parallelism.

- 883 • **Linear Discriminant Analysis** – According to the research conducted by Bagheri
884 et al. [79], a simultaneous classification of mental workload and stress levels could
885 be performed using the LDA classifier. Eighteen healthy participants coped with
886 arithmetic tasks of various difficulties to induce mental stress (low and high) and public
887 speaking presentation in front of a jury to evoke different affective states (relaxed and
888 stressed). Frequency domain features were extracted and classified using a regularized
889 LDA algorithm combined with TL, which used data from another 17 subjects during
890 the training. The algorithm proved to be more suitable for detecting the stress level and
891 achieved a higher accuracy (ACC = 84.10%) compared to the workload classification
892 (ACC = 77.50%). In the future, the effectiveness of the method also needs to be
893 verified during online classification.

- 894 • **Support Vector Machines** – The use of SVM to recognize emotions in patients
895 with DOC, such as coma or vegetative state, who cannot adequately express their
896 emotions, was addressed by Huang et al. [21]. Emotions (negative and positive) were
897 evoked in subjects by watching video clips. Features from the frequency domain were
898 extracted and normalized from the signals and classified in real-time using linear kernel
899 SVM. This approach was tested in ten healthy subjects with an average accuracy of
900 91.50% and, in eight patients with DOC, where the accuracy of classification dropped
901 significantly, to 58.50%. A very similar trend was also observed in the study reported
902 by Pan et al. [86], who detected SVM awareness in four healthy subjects, seven patients
903 with DOC and one with LIS. In healthy subjects, the average accuracy of classification
904 was the highest (ACC = 95.00%), in patients with LIS (ACC = 75.33%), it was
905 significantly lower, and, in patients with DOC (ACC = 59.94%), it was the lowest.
906 Therefore, according to the results in [21], it is necessary to test the algorithm on a
907 larger number of subjects with DOC, thus increasing the reliability of the algorithm. It
908 is also important to test this approach on self-induced emotions in daily life scenarios,
909 where the signals usually have a much lower amplitude and focus on recognizing more
910 types of emotions.

911 Classification of emotions into two, but also into three and five classes using multi-class
912 SVM algorithm and EEG signals was addressed by Atkinson et al. [85]. The highest
913 accuracy was achieved using only two classification classes (ACC = 73.10%). With an
914 increasing number of classes, the accuracy of the algorithm decreased to 61.52% and
915 46.00% using three and five classes, respectively. Due to the time-consuming nature,
916 only a few settings of the model have been tested, so a more suitable setting can
917 contribute to improving the accuracy.

918 Interesting use of SVM within the passive fNIRS-BCI was found by Gateau et al.

919 [80], who used it to distinguish two levels (low and high) of the working memory of
920 pilots during piloting aircraft. A total of 28 pilots were divided into two groups, one
921 part operating real aircraft while the other a simulator. All pilots performed the same
922 serial memorization tasks during the flight (repeating series of easy and hard air traffic
923 control instructions). In both types of experiments, SVM achieved an average accuracy
924 of 77.50% in the online classification. Nevertheless, the authors proposed to optimize
925 the classifier in order to achieve higher accuracy and reliability.

926 • **Logistic Regression** – Logistic regression (LR) is a simple supervised learning algo-
927 rithm for binary classification. The concept of the method is based on the probabilistic
928 concept and the sigmoid S-shaped curve [159]. Pahwa et al. [87] used LR to classify
929 wakeful and sleep-like states in four subjects with epilepsy and implanted subdural
930 ECoG electrode grids. The authors assumed that cognitive states (wakefulness and
931 sleep) have different spectral topographies. In online classification, LR worked best
932 ($ACC = 81.35\%$) when high gamma band signals were selected. However, in one of
933 the subjects, the classification accuracy was low in the online phase, despite the high
934 accuracy in the training phase, which was probably due to the LF over-fitting during
935 training.

Table 4: Overview of AI-based algorithms and their use for mental condition estimation.

Author, source	Technique	Algorithm	Task	Data/Dataset	Result
Casson [77]	EEG	ANN	workload classification	CSAC 2011	ACC = 72.57%
Sanchez-Reolid et al. [83]	EEG	MLP	emotion estimation	16 healthy subjects	ACC = 85.00%
Appriou et al. [32]	EEG	CNN	emotion estimation	DEAP	ACC = 45.51%
			workload classification	22 subjects performing mental tasks	ACC = 68.23%
Gao et al. [82]	EEG	CNN	driver fatigue detection	8 subjects using driving simulator	ACC = 97.37%
Tanveer et al. [81]	fNIRS	CNN	driver fatigue detection	13 subjects using driving simulator	ACC = 99.30%
Asgher et al. [78]	fNIRS	CNN LSTM	workload classification	15 healthy subjects	ACC = 87.45%
					ACC = 89.31%
Jirayucharoensak et al. [84]	EEG	PCA-AE	emotion estimation	DEAP	ACC = 52.74%
Bagheri et al. [79]	EEG	LDA-TL	workload classification	18 healthy subjects	ACC = 77.50%
			stress level detection		ACC = 84.10%
Huang et al. [21]	EEG	SVM	emotion estimation	10 healthy subjects	ACC = 91.50%
				8 subjects with DOC	ACC = 58.50%
Pan et al. [86]	EEG	SVM	awareness detection	4 healthy subjects	ACC = 95.00%
				1 subject with LIS	ACC = 75.33%
				7 subjects with DOC	ACC = 59.94%
Atkinson et al. [85]	EEG	SVM	emotion estimation	DEAP	ACC = 60.21%
Gateau et al. [80]	fNIRS	SVM	memory load estimation	28 subjects piloting an aircraft	ACC = 77.50%
Pahwa et al. [87]	ECoG	LR	wake/sleep states detection	4 subjects with epilepsy	ACC = 81.35%

Cognitive State Assessment Competition 2011 Dataset (CSAC 2011) [160] – 118 EEG recordings from 8 subjects performing a flight simulator task
 Database for Emotion Analysis using Physiological Signals (DEAP) [158] – EEG from 32 healthy subjects watching music videos

936 3.5. Motor Imagery-based BCI Systems

937 MI is the most represented area for the implementation of AI- and ML-based algorithms
938 for the classification of brain signals. In the case of MI tasks, brain signals are generated
939 spontaneously without the need for external stimuli, and control actions are performed
940 on the basis of spontaneous mental activity [161]. The most common use of spontaneous
941 BCI systems, which received an attention from scientists, required the user to imagine the
942 movement of a limb and the classifier to distinguish which limb [88, 89, 90, 91, 92] or
943 movement type (e.g. flexion/extension or open/close hand) [93, 94, 95] it was. Further
944 use of spontaneous BCI systems focused on specific practical applications, such as robot
945 [96, 97, 98] or robot arm control [99, 100, 162], lower-limb [101] or hand [102] exoskeleton
946 control, wheelchair [22, 104, 103] and vehicle control [105, 163]. An overview of applications
947 is summarized in this subsection and in Table 5.

948 • **Artificial Neural Network** – According to the results of research conducted by
949 Yaacoub et al. [88], the implementation of ANN was suitable for the classification
950 of left/right hand movement MI tasks. The hidden layer of the network contained
951 seven neurons, and temporal and spectral signal features were used as inputs to the
952 ANN. Using all available features (i.e. 12,336 for each signal), the ANN achieved
953 a high accuracy of 88.10%, but at the expense of the high complexity of the EEG-
954 BCI system. To remove this limitation, the authors incorporated a GA algorithm for
955 feature selection, which selected only useful features, and discarded those that could
956 be misleading. The GA parameters were set to 50 chromosomes, 20 iterations, and the
957 mutation probability was 5%. In this case, only 61 signal features and 5 neurons in
958 the hidden layer were used, leading to a significant reduction in the complexity of the
959 system allowing a real-time classification. In addition, the accuracy of the classification
960 was slightly increased ($ACC = 90.50\%$). Also, the fact that, with an increasing number
961 of neurons in the hidden layer, the classification did not significantly improve (accuracy
962 fluctuated around a constant value), but the complexity of the system and the time
963 required for simulation increased, was an important finding. Therefore, it was possible
964 to select a low number of neurons in the hidden layer without degrading the accuracy.

965 The same finding was also made by Li et al. [22], who therefore, used 22 neurons in
966 the input layer, 4 neurons in the output layer and only 10 neurons in the hidden layer
967 when implementing ANN for the classification of the wheelchair movements control.
968 To improve the classification accuracy, the network was trained using the grey wolf
969 optimizer (GWO) instead of the classic BP algorithm. GWO is one of the swarm
970 intelligence techniques and is inspired by the natural hunting process of the grey wolves.
971 The algorithm was tested while classifying EEG signals obtained from six healthy
972 subjects and three subjects with ALS. In healthy participants, the accuracy of the
973 classification was high ($ACC = 96.67\%$), but, in subjects with ALS, the accuracy was
974 lower ($ACC = 88.33\%$), which could be caused by the need for a longer training time
975 in these patients. The experiments were performed only offline and it is necessary to
976 verify their effectiveness in online classification.

977 • **Multilayer Perceptron** – MLP proved to be effective for the classification of fMRI
978 signals in robot arm control in a study by Minati et al. [99]. The signals were measured
979 in five healthy subjects using the Achieva 3T clinical MR system (Philips Healthcare
980 BV, Best, Netherlands) with a 32-channel head coil. The MLP contained 94 – 152
981 neurons in the input layer (depending on an activation overlap), 8 neurons in the
982 hidden layer and 4 output neurons. The average accuracy of the system reached
983 92.00%, the median action recognition time was 24.3 s and the robot execution time
984 was 17.7 s. In order for the system to be used in real-time, it is necessary to overcome
985 its time-consuming nature.

986 • **Bayesian Network** – Bayesian Network (BN) is a probabilistic model that uses a
987 graph representation to display probabilistic relationships between individual variables.
988 BN is expressed by an acyclically oriented graph, where each of the multiple nodes
989 corresponds to one random variable. The edges (relationships) between the nodes show
990 the probability dependence between the variables, which is calculated using statistical
991 methods [164, 89, 165].

992 To increase the classification accuracy, BN was successfully combined with the SVM
993 algorithm by He et al. [89] in the classification of EEG signals obtained during
994 hands/feet/tongue MI. The authors also examined the effect of the length of imag-
995 ing time on the accuracy of the algorithm. It was found that if the duration of MI
996 imaging was less than 0.2 s, the performance of the algorithm was poor (there was
997 not enough MI information to make discrimination). On the other hand, if the image
998 lasted longer than 3 s, there was also a significant reduction in the accuracy of the
999 classification (the density of MI information was low). The most accurate classification
1000 was achieved after 1.5 s motor imaging with 0.2 s time duration. However, to use the
1001 algorithm in real applications, it is necessary to collect a large amount of training data
1002 for learning the accurate conditional probability.

1003 • **Extreme Learning Machine** – The extreme learning machine (ELM) is a forward
1004 network with one hidden layer. It differs from the classic ANN in that it does not need
1005 to set a large number of training parameters (only the number of hidden layer nodes).
1006 The number of hidden layer nodes can be set adaptively and the input weights and
1007 hidden layer biases can be assigned randomly. The output weights of hidden nodes can
1008 be set in one step, using the least square method, without having to perform several
1009 iterations. Compared to the ANN with the BP learning algorithm, the training speed
1010 and generalization ability of ELM are significantly better [166].

1011 The multikernel ELM has been successfully implemented for the classification of MI
1012 hand and foot movement by Zhang et al. [167]. The principle of the approach consisted
1013 in the simultaneous use of two types of kernels (Gaussian and polynomial, which were
1014 able to effectively map features extracted using a common spatial pattern and provide
1015 better discriminant information. An accuracy of 87.50% was achieved with the right
1016 hand/foot MI classification, but the accuracy was lower with the left/right hand MI
1017 classification (ACC = 78.90%). To improve the accuracy, the authors recommended

1018 proposing a more sophisticated strategy for estimating kernel balance parameters, such
1019 as semi-definite programming or ensemble learning.

1020 ELM has also been successful in classifying ECoG signals in study by Zhang et al.
1021 [168] during left pinky and tongue MI tasks. The optimal number of neurons in the
1022 hidden layer was 33 and the *sine* and *sigmoid* activation function worked effectively.
1023 In addition to high accuracy (ACC = 92.31%), the computational time for ELM was
1024 lower compared to SVM. Testing the proposed approach only on signals from one
1025 subject was the limitation.

1026 • **Deep Belief Network** – The deep belief network (DBN) is a type of ANN containing
1027 multiple layers with hidden units and connections between the individual layers, but
1028 not between the units within each layer. In essence, it is a combination of several
1029 unsupervised ANNs, such as restricted Boltzmann machines or AEs, where the hidden
1030 layer of each individual network serves as a visible layer for another network. The
1031 time-efficient training process and the need for a limited number of training samples
1032 are the main advantages of this architecture [169].

1033 Fu et al. [93] used DBN to classify fNIRS signals measured during flexion and exten-
1034 sion of left and right arms MI tasks. Before the creation of the DBN, two restricted
1035 Boltzmann machines were first trained separately. After the training phase was com-
1036 pleted, DBN was created by combining them. The experiments were performed on
1037 ten healthy subjects, with an average accuracy of 81.27%. The network was fast and
1038 suitable for an online BCI system, but the disadvantage of this approach consisted in
1039 the use of a low feature dimension, which would have to be increased when used in
1040 online systems.

1041 • **Convolutional Neural Network** – CNN has also been used frequently in the field
1042 of MI. Its effectiveness has been verified experimentally by Amin et al. [170] when
1043 classifying the hands/feet/tongue MI. The authors proposed a multilevel feature fu-
1044 sion model, which consisted of pretraining and transfer learning, multilevel feature
1045 extraction and weight-based feature fusion from all convolution layers using fully con-
1046 nected layers. This led to the preservation of features at each convolution level. The
1047 average accuracy of the algorithm was 74.50%. Similar accuracy (ACC = 74.20%)
1048 was achieved by CNN in the classification of right/left hand MI, see Xu et al. [171].
1049 This approach was based on the preprocessing of signals using a short time Fourier
1050 transform (STFT) and their conversion into time-frequency spectrum images, which
1051 served as inputs for deep transfer CNN. Low-level features in the front-layers of CNN
1052 were used for classification as they were universal for different but related tasks. Ierac-
1053 itano et al. [94] achieved a significantly higher accuracy (ACC = 90.10%) with CNN
1054 at open/close hand MI classification. This could be due to the incorporation of an in-
1055 verse problem solution and extraction of the cortical EEG sources. The beamforming
1056 technique was used for the reconstruction of EEG sources (time-source maps), which
1057 served as inputs to the CNN classifier. However, the time-consuming nature of the
1058 CNN is an obstacle for real-time application.

1059 A comparison of four types of CNN architectures (EEGNet, DeepConvNet, AlexNet
1060 and LeNet) was discussed by Krishnan et al. [172]. The input EEG signals were first
1061 decomposed into four modes using variational mode decomposition (VMD). STFT
1062 was applied to these VMD modes, which provided a spectrum images of individual
1063 modes. Only the spectrum images corresponding to the EEG were retained and used
1064 as inputs for CNN. The most accurate classification in the four-classes MI (left/right
1065 hand/foot/tongue MI) was achieved by the EEGNet architecture, which also had a
1066 less complex structure than DeepConvNet and AlexNet.

1067 CNN has also proved to be useful in controlling an assistance robot using EEG-based
1068 BCI, as shown by Kuhner et al. [96]. ConvNet architecture was used to classify the
1069 five-classes of MI (drive from one location to another, pick up/drop an object, pour
1070 liquids from bottles into cups, and take a drink to the user). In online testing, the
1071 classification was successful in 76.90% of cases. However, it is necessary to verify the
1072 accuracy of classifiers in patients with motor disabilities, for whom the use of the
1073 assistance robot is primarily intended.

1074 • **Capsule Network** – Capsule network (CapsNet) is an extended variant of conven-
1075 tional CNN that allows better modelling of hierarchical relationships. The algorithm
1076 is based on the idea of adding a group of neurons, called capsules, to the conventional
1077 CNN and reusing the output of these capsules to create a more stable representation
1078 for higher capsules [173].

1079 The combination of STFT and CapsNet was tested for the left/right hand MI clas-
1080 sification by Ha et al. [174]. The input EEG signals from each electrode were first
1081 transformed into 2-D images using STFT and these were used as inputs for CapsNet.
1082 CapsNet classified EEG signals with higher accuracy than conventional CNN, but the
1083 training time was longer with CapsNet. Further improvement of network performance
1084 could be achieved by implementing new techniques for network hyperparameter’s op-
1085 timization.

1086 • **Long Short Term Memory** – For the prediction and classification of time-series
1087 ECoG data, LSTM was implemented by Rashid et al. [175]. The LSTM input layer
1088 contained 64 neurons, the hidden layer contained 100 neurons, 2 neurons were used in
1089 a fully connected layer, and a softmax layer and a sigmoid layer were also employed.
1090 During training, the number of epochs and iterations was set to 150 and 1,500, re-
1091 spectively. The accuracy of the algorithm was stable from 240 iterations. In the test
1092 phase, the algorithm reached 97.00% accuracy at two-classes MI (left pinky/tongue).
1093 Accuracies greater than 90.00% in the classification of four-classes MI (index flex-
1094 ion/extension and wrist flexion/extension) using LSTM were achieved by Schwemmer
1095 et al. [95]. Data recorded in one subject with spinal cord injury using iCor technique
1096 was first decomposed by WT (*Daubechies4* mother wavelet and 11 levels of decompo-
1097 sition) and classified by LSTM, which was additionally combined with CNN. However,
1098 the complexity of the approach and the long training time were very limiting.

1099 Despite the high accuracy of invasive ECoG and iCor techniques, LSTM performed
1100 less efficiently when tested on EEG signals. Luo et al. [90] achieved an accuracy of
1101 81.52% in the classification of two-classes MI (left/right hand) and its accuracy was
1102 even lower in four-classes MI (left/right hand/foot/tongue), only 72.58%. In addition,
1103 the computational complexity of LSTM was high as well as the storage needs. To
1104 overcome these limitations, the solution could be to use a gated recurrent unit (GRU)
1105 network, which is very similar to LSTM. Unlike LSTM, the GRU uses fewer training
1106 parameters, less memory and is faster with better performance.

1107 • **Linear Discriminant Analysis** – The LDA was used to classify left/right wrist MI
1108 measured using the fNIRS technique by Naseer et al. [176]. During the experiments,
1109 it was found that if the classifier was applied to the entire signal segment when the
1110 wrist task was performed (10 s segment), the performance of the algorithm was low
1111 (ACC = 78.18%). However, if the initial 2 s span and/or the time span after the peak
1112 value was omitted, and the classifier was used only for the 2 – 7 s section, the average
1113 accuracy was higher (ACC = 82.42%).

1114 The use of clustering LDA (CLDA) for four-classes of wrist MI (up/down/left/right
1115 movements) signals, which were recorded using a 306-channel whole-head MEG system
1116 during the experiments performed by Zhang et al. [177], proved to be efficient (ACC =
1117 87.00%). In this case, the WT method was used for feature extraction (*symlet2* mother
1118 wavelet and six levels of decomposition), where each wavelet coefficient was considered
1119 as a signal feature. Using CLDA, the within-group correlation was maximized and the
1120 between-group correlation was minimized, leading to accurate classification of signal
1121 features. However, in patients with LIS lower accuracy can be expected and it is
1122 therefore necessary to ensure the reliability of the method also for these subjects.

1123 The LDA has proved to be a very universal method suitable for a number of different
1124 classification tasks, including rehabilitation, as shown in experiments conducted by
1125 Xu et al. [178]. For the purpose of controlling active ankle-foot orthosis, the LDA
1126 was combined with locality preserving projection (LPP) for dimensionality reduction
1127 and reached a true positive rate (TPR) of 73.00%. Another effective application of
1128 LDA was in vehicle destination selection in a study proposed by Fan et al. [105],
1129 The PCA method was implemented for feature extraction and the LDA classified the
1130 extracted EEG signal features. The authors did not notice a significant difference in
1131 the performance of the algorithm when testing both in the laboratory (ACC = 99.07%)
1132 and in real driving conditions (ACC = 98.93%). The application of LDA also proved
1133 to be very promising in robot control using EEG signals, according to the findings
1134 in the study introduced by Aljalal et al. [97]. However, the experimental results of
1135 Batula et al. [98] revealed very low classification accuracy (ACC = 29.72%) for virtual
1136 and physical robot control when fNIRS signals were used. Significant improvements
1137 are, therefore, still needed in this area in order to be able to use robots in real-world
1138 conditions.

1139 • **Spectral Regression Discriminant Analysis** – Spectral regression discriminant

1140 analysis (SRDA) is based on casting the discriminant analysis into a regression frame-
1141 work. Hence, SRDA addresses only a set of regularized least-squares problems without
1142 the need for eigen decomposition of dense matrices. This leads to a higher computing
1143 speed and memory savings compared to LDA [179].

1144 To improve the classification accuracy of the SRDA algorithm, Liu et al. [179] used
1145 an optimization method called the firefly algorithm (FA) to select the optimal set of
1146 features. FA was able to adaptively find the optimal signal features extracted using
1147 the common spatial pattern, but in some cases, the algorithm got stuck in the local
1148 optimum. Therefore, FA has been combined with learning automaton (LA). LA is
1149 an ML-based adaptive decision-making system operating in an unknown environment
1150 that performs current action based on past experiences. The optimal set of features
1151 was then used for subsequent classification using SRDA. The combined approach was
1152 able to effectively classify four-classes MI (left/right hand/foot/tongue), and it used
1153 a lower number of signal features compared to the use of GA or PSO. For the use in
1154 real-time applications, it is necessary to reduce the time-consuming nature.

- 1155 • **Support Vector Machines** – For the purpose of selecting the optimal feature set,
1156 the SVM was combined with the nature-inspired optimization technique, specifically
1157 with differential evolution (DE) by Baig et al. [91]. Out of a total of 236 signal features
1158 extracted by the common spatial pattern, the combination of DE-SVM methods was
1159 able to achieve an average accuracy of 96.02% using only ten features. The low speed
1160 of the algorithm was the same limitation as in [179].

1161 According to the findings of Fang et al. [180], the performance of the common spatial
1162 pattern method is negatively affected by dispersion in the operational frequency band
1163 and the presence of interference. Therefore, the authors recommended using an ap-
1164 proach based on Riemannian geometry for feature extraction, which is able to obtain
1165 features from spatial covariance matrices of the EEG signal. The subsequent classifi-
1166 cation of four MI tasks (left-hand, right-hand, feet, and tongue imaginary movement)
1167 using the SVM method achieved the average accuracy of 77.70% and 86.90% for two
1168 tested datasets.

1169 The suitability of the Riemannian approach for feature extraction was also demon-
1170 strated during the experiments conducted by Chu et al. [181]. The method was
1171 tested on 12 healthy volunteers during 6-class MI tasks (elbow flexion/extension, wrist
1172 supination/pronation, and hand close/open). In this case, the SVM method (ACC =
1173 79.70%) was slightly outperformed by the LDA method (ACC = 80.50%) during the
1174 classification phase. However, in the future, it is necessary to verify this approach also
1175 when distinguishing simultaneous movements.

1176 Fast and accurate decoding of finger movements (6-classes MI in 12 epileptic subjects)
1177 from ECoG through Riemannian features was achieved in a study by Yao et al. [3]
1178 Here, the SVM method (ACC = 76.00%) was also slightly outperformed by the light
1179 gradient boosting machine (lightGBM) method, which achieved an accuracy of 77.00%.
1180 By implementing the feature selection method, the computation time was reduced

1181 while remaining the overall performance. In the future, it will be necessary to evaluate
1182 the stability of the algorithm in real-world environments.

1183 To achieve higher accuracy of the SVM, Sadiq et al. [182] combined least-square SVM
1184 (LS-SVM) with adaptive empirical wavelet transform (EWT) for two-classes EEG-
1185 based MI (right hand/foot) classification. The input EEG signals were decomposed
1186 into individual frequency modes by EWT and those modes with the maximum value
1187 of Welch power spectral density were selected for further processing. Signal features
1188 based on instantaneous amplitude and frequency were extracted from these modes and
1189 used for LS-SVM classification. In order to make the algorithm more time-efficient,
1190 only 18 of the 118 EEG channels were used for processing. The average speed of
1191 the algorithm was 12 s, thus allowing its use in an online application. However, the
1192 appropriate channels and EWT modes were selected manually, which was a major
1193 obstacle for online implementation. In the future, it is, therefore, necessary to make
1194 these selections using an automated algorithm that will be able to adapt to individual
1195 subjects. A similar approach proved successful in the case of fNIRS signals during
1196 hand/finger MI classification, as shown by Li et al. [183]. However, the empirical
1197 mode decomposition (EMD) algorithm was used instead of EWT to decompose the
1198 input signal into individual modes. The combination of the methods reported by
1199 Shiraishi et al. [184], where SVM was combined with dynamic mode decomposition
1200 (DMD) to classify ECoG signals during upper limb MI, also proved promising.

1201 In the field of rehabilitation and walking assistance, the SVM algorithm was used to
1202 classify EEG signals under the lower-limb exoskeleton control in a study by Wang et
1203 al. [101]. Using the common spatial pattern method for feature extraction, irrelevant
1204 information and noise from the signals were eliminated, and the SVM classification
1205 accuracy was 80.83% in real-time testing (in offline testing, the accuracy was about
1206 10.00% higher). Asgher et al. [102] verified the functionality of the SVM classifier in
1207 the robotic exoskeleton hand control, but instead of EEG, brain signals were captured
1208 using a 12-channel fNIRS system. The use of only two signal features (mean and
1209 slope) leading to an average value of $ACC = 87.90\%$ in online testing on 14 healthy
1210 subjects proved to be the most effective. However, the results showed that the real-
1211 time application can only be used with a limited possibilities compared to EEG, which
1212 has a higher information transfer rate and faster control translations. Last but not
1213 least, the SVM algorithm with a high success rate (SR) of 94.70% was used to classify
1214 EEG signals sensed during wheelchair control in an indoor environment by Zhang et
1215 al. [104]. However, the disadvantage of this approach consisted in the possibility
1216 of using the wheelchair only in a room with webcams. Devising a system to ensure
1217 functionality in the classification of signals during movement in complex indoor and
1218 outdoor areas is necessary.

- 1219 • **K-Nearest Neighbors** – According to a comparison made by Chaudhary et al. [185],
1220 the KNN proved to be the most suitable algorithm in comparison with other methods
1221 (e.g. SVM, decision trees or LDA) for right hand/foot MI classification. The au-

1222 thors chose temporal moment based features, which were extracted from subbands ob-
1223 tained by decomposition of input EEG signals using the flexible analytic WT (FAWT)
1224 method. The ensembles KNN method based on random subspaces was used for the
1225 subsequent classification and reached an average value of $ACC = 95.98\%$. In the case
1226 of classification of the fNIRS signals during six classes of finger tapping MI tasks, the
1227 KNN algorithm achieved comparable performance with the RF method (in both cases
1228 $ACC = 75.00\%$), see Khan et al. [186]. However, both methods were outperformed by
1229 the extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) algorithm, which achieved a slightly higher
1230 accuracy of 77.00% . The authors noted that a deeper analysis of signals in the tem-
1231 poral and spatial domain is needed to increase the accuracy of individual methods.

1232 • **Fuzzy Logic** – The self-regulated adaptive resonance theory (ART) based neuro-
1233 fuzzy classifier, called the self-regulated supervised Gaussian fuzzy adaptive system
1234 ART (SRSG-FasArt), was implemented by Jafarifarmand et al. [187] to capture non-
1235 stationarities of EEG signals and their classification in four-classes MI tasks. This
1236 approach was automatically able to create, adjust or prune fuzzy rules according to
1237 the knowledge content in the training data. The proposed algorithm was thus able to
1238 better generalize the data and reduce the risk of over-training. The disadvantage of
1239 the algorithm consisted in the need to set appropriate parameters to achieve accurate
1240 classification. The optimal setting could be found by implementing an optimization
1241 technique.

1242 Ko et al. [92] introduced a concept based on multi-modal fuzzy fusion (MFF) to im-
1243 prove the classification of EEG signals recorded during two-class MI (left/right hand)
1244 and four-class MI (left/right hand/foot/tongue). The principle was based on incor-
1245 porating Choquet or Sugeno FIs to connect the resulting probabilities obtained using
1246 several different classifiers, such as KNN, LDA and quadratic discriminant analysis.
1247 The results of the experiments showed that the choice of the frequency band from which
1248 the features were extracted had a great influence on the accuracy of the classification
1249 (alpha and beta bands were the most relevant for MI tasks). Furthermore, it turned
1250 out that Choquet integral was slightly more effective in both four-class and two-class
1251 classification. However, in the case of the four-class classification, the accuracy of the
1252 algorithm was significantly reduced compared to the two-class classification (by up
1253 to 14.75%) and its improvement is therefore necessary for this task. Choquet FIs in
1254 combination with PSO also proved to be a suitable choice for robotic arm control in
1255 the study reported by Wu et al. [100]. The PSO algorithm allowed regulating subject-
1256 specific parameters when assigning optimal confidence levels for classifiers. In online
1257 testing, the algorithm achieved an average accuracy of 86.00% , but it was two-class
1258 MI, so more experiments are needed with the more advanced BCI system allowing
1259 multidirectional movements of robotic arm.

Table 5: Overview of AI-based algorithms and their use for motor imagery.

Author, source	Technique	Algorithm	Task	Data/Dataset	Result
Yaacoub et al. [88]	EEG	GA-ANN	left/right hand MI	BCI Competition III-3b Dataset	ACC = 90.50%
Li et al. [22]	EEG	GWO-ANN	wheelchair control	6 healthy subjects 3 subjects with ALS	ACC = 96.67% ACC = 88.33%
Minati et al. [99]	fMRI	MLP	robot arm control	5 healthy subjects	ACC = 92.00%
He et al. [89]	EEG	BN-SVM	left/right hand/foot/tongue MI	BCI Competition III-3a Dataset BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset	ACC = 89.33% ACC = 67.56%
Zhang et al. [167]	EEG	ELM	right hand/foot MI left/right hand MI	BCI Competition III-4a Dataset BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset	ACC = 87.50% ACC = 78.90%
Zhang et al. [168]	ECoG	ELM	left pinky/tongue MI	BCI Competition III-1 Dataset	ACC = 92.31%
Fu et al. [93]	fNIRS	DBN	arms flexion/extension MI	10 healthy subjects	ACC = 81.27%
Amin et al. [170]	EEG	CNN	left/right hand/foot/tongue MI	BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset	ACC = 74.50%
Xu et al. [171]	EEG	STFT-CNN	left/right hand MI	BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset	ACC = 74.20%
Ieracitano et al. [94]	EEG	CNN	open/close hand MI	15 healthy subjects	ACC = 90.10%
Krishnan et al. [172]	EEG	VMD-STFT-CNN	left/right hand/foot/tongue MI	BCI Competition III-3a Dataset BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset	ACC = 91.37% ACC = 94.41%
Kuhner et al. [96]	EEG	CNN	service robot control	4 healthy subjects	ACC = 76.90%
Ha et al. [174]	EEG	STFT-CapsNet	left/right hand MI	BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset	ACC = 78.44%
Rashid et al. [175]	ECoG	LSTM	left pinky/tongue MI	BCI Competition III-1 Dataset	ACC = 97.00%
Schwemmer et al. [95]	iCor	WT-LSTM-CNN	index/wrist flexion and extension MI	1 subject with spinal cord injury	ACC > 90.00%
Luo et al. [90]	EEG	LSTM	left/right hand/foot/tongue MI left/right hand MI	BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset	ACC = 72.58% ACC = 81.52%
Naseer et al. [176]	fNIRS	LDA	left/right wrist MI	10 healthy subjects	ACC = 82.42%
Zhang et al. [177]	MEG	WT-CLDA	up/down/left/right wrist MI	5 healthy subjects	ACC = 87.00%
Xu et al. [178]	EEG	LPP-LDA	ankle-foot orthosis control	10 healthy subjects	TPR = 73.00%
Fan et al. [105]	EEG	PCA-LDA	vehicle control	16 healthy subjects	ACC = 99.00%
Aljalal et al. [97]	EEG	LDA	robot control	8 healthy subjects	ACC = 80.92%

BCI Competition III-1 Dataset [154] – ECoG from 1 subject performing 2-classes MI (left pinky, tongue)
 BCI Competition III-3a Dataset [154] – EEG from 3 subjects performing 4-classes MI (left hand, right hand, foot, tongue)
 BCI Competition III-3b Dataset [154] – EEG from 3 subjects performing non-stationary 2-classes MI (right hand, left hand)
 BCI Competition III-4a Dataset [154] – EEG from 5 subjects performing 2-classes MI (right hand, foot)
 BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset [113] – EEG from 9 subjects performing 4-classes MI (left hand, right hand, feet, tongue)
 BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset [113] – EEG from 9 subjects performing 2-classes MI (right hand, left hand)
 BCI Competition IV-4 Dataset [113]– ECoG from 3 subjects performing 5-classes MI (thumb, index, middle, ring, little finger flexion)

Author, source	Technique	Algorithm	Task	Data/Dataset	Result
Batula et al. [98]	fNIRS	LDA	robot control	12 healthy subjects	ACC = 29.72%
Liu et al. [179]	EEG	FA-LA-SRDA	left/right hand/foot/tongue MI	BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset 4 healthy subjects	ACC = 70.20% ACC = 68.00%
Baig et al. [91]	EEG	DE-SVM	right hand/foot MI	BCI Competition III-4a Dataset	ACC = 96.02%
Fang et al. [22]	EEG	SVM	left/right hand/foot/tongue MI left/right hand MI	BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset	ACC = 77.70% ACC = 86.90%
Chu et al. [181]	EEG	SVM LDA	elbow/wrist/hand MI	12 healthy subjects	ACC = 79.70% ACC = 80.50%
Yao et al. [188]	ECoG	SVM lightGBM	fingers flexion MI	BCI Competition IV-4 Dataset 9 epileptic subjects	ACC = 76.00% ACC = 77.00%
Sadiq et al. [182]	EEG	EWT-LS-SVM	right hand/foot MI	BCI Competition III-4a Dataset	ACC = 95.19%
Li et al. [183]	fNIRS	EMD-SVM	hands/finger MI	6 healthy subjects	ACC = 89.12%
Shiraishi et al. [184]	ECoG	DMD-SVM	upper limb movements MI	5 subjects with brain stroke and 6 subjects with epilepsy	ACC = 79.80%
Wang et al. [101]	EEG	SVM	lower-limb exoskeleton control	4 healthy subjects	ACC = 80.83%
Asgher et al. [102]	fNIRS	SVM	hand exoskeleton control	14 healthy subjects	ACC = 87.90%
Zhang et al. [104]	EEG	SVM	wheelchair control	9 subjects	SR = 94.70%
Chaudhary et al. [185]	EEG	FAWT-KNN	right hand/foot MI	BCI Competition III-4a Dataset	ACC = 95.98%
Khan et al. [23]	fNIRS	KNN RF XGBoost	finger tapping MI	24 healthy subjects	ACC = 75.00% ACC = 75.00% ACC = 77.00%
Jafarifarmand et al. [187]	EEG	SRSG-FasArt	left/right hand/foot/tongue MI	BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset	ACC = 88.55%
Ko et al. [92]	EEG	MFV	left/right hand left/right hand/foot/tongue MI	10 healthy subjects BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset	ACC = 78.81% ACC = 64.06%
Wu et al. [100]	EEG	FIs-PSO	robotic arm control	10 healthy subjects	ACC = 86.00%

BCI Competition III-1 Dataset [154] – ECoG from 1 subject performing 2-classes MI (left pinky, tongue)

BCI Competition III-3a Dataset [154] – EEG from 3 subjects performing 4-classes MI (left hand, right hand, foot, tongue)

BCI Competition III-3b Dataset [154] – EEG from 3 subjects performing non-stationary 2-classes MI (right hand, left hand)

BCI Competition III-4a Dataset [154] – EEG from 5 subjects performing 2-classes MI (right hand, foot)

BCI Competition IV-2a Dataset [113] – EEG from 9 subjects performing 4-classes MI (left hand, right hand, feet, tongue)

BCI Competition IV-2b Dataset [113] – EEG from 9 subjects performing 2-classes MI (right hand, left hand)

BCI Competition IV-4 Dataset [113]– ECoG from 3 subjects performing 5-classes MI (thumb, index, middle, ring, little finger flexion)

1260 4. Discussion and Summary

1261 The findings in this review have shown that current research in the field of BCIs focuses on
1262 improvement of conventional EEG technique as well as alternative non-invasive fNIRS, MEG
1263 and fMRI or invasive ECoG and iCor methods. The processing and analysis of the brain
1264 signals are very challenging due to their non-stationary and nonlinear nature. In addition,
1265 brain signals are generated by the summation of the activity of an extremely high number of
1266 neurons, and their character is usually irregular and chaotic. Therefore, the implementation
1267 of AI- and ML-based algorithms within BCI systems is directly encouraged and research in
1268 this area has been very popular in recent years. However, up-to-date, there is no standardized
1269 methodology for assessing accuracy in the processing and analysis of brain signals, so it is
1270 difficult to objectively compare the results obtained in individual studies. In addition, for
1271 testing, the authors use non-uniform data (their own or from different datasets) recorded in
1272 non-identical subjects involving both healthy participants and patients with different types
1273 of disabilities. The results may also be affected by the type of recording hardware device
1274 used.

1275 This section aims to:

- 1276 1. compare the results of individual algorithms (both subjectively and objectively), sum-
1277 marize the important findings and recommendations for future research, see subsec-
1278 tion 4.1,
- 1279 2. outline the remaining challenges that need to be addressed in connection with BCI
1280 systems and AI or ML. These challenges are further discussed in subsection 4.2.

1281 4.1. Summary of Findings and Recommendations

1282 The calibration phase used to train the subject-specific classifier is an important part
1283 of BCIs for converting brain signals into meaningful instructions. In practical use, this
1284 step has proved to be very demanding both in terms of time and storing large amounts
1285 of data from each subject. Moreover, it was a tedious process for the users, in which some
1286 subjects, especially patients with some type of disability, may have had difficulty maintaining
1287 attention. Therefore, according to the findings in this research, the authors successfully
1288 implemented AI- and ML-based algorithms to create BCI systems with a reduced calibration
1289 time of up to 90.00% or a completely calibration-free device. CNN proved to be the most
1290 suitable method in this area, since in addition to eliminating the need for calibration, a
1291 relatively high classification accuracy was subsequently achieved, see Table 1. However,
1292 CNN was limited by high computational complexity, so it would be appropriate to focus the
1293 research on simple and fast ML-based techniques (e.g. SVM in combination with TL), that
1294 would be more suitable for real-time applications. At the same time, it turned out that,
1295 with these calibration-free or reduced time calibration systems, lower accuracy was achieved
1296 in the subsequent classification for MI tasks than for ERP tasks. A similar trend, i.e. more
1297 complex decoding of MI tasks, was also observed in [189], and further improvements in this
1298 area will be needed.

1299 In terms of noise suppression, conventional filtering or advanced signal processing algo-
1300 rithms can be used with most of the mentioned measurement techniques. However, in the
1301 case of EEG signals, the elimination of interference is very challenging, as they have low am-
1302 plitudes and are usually significantly contaminated with wide spectral artifacts. In addition,
1303 a regular morphological pattern cannot be observed with EEG, as in the case of measuring
1304 cardiac activity using the ECG, and it can be difficult to distinguish noise from the useful
1305 signal. The results summarized in Table 2 showed that when using a single algorithm based
1306 on AI or ML, the noise suppression was not effective enough and the value of the ACC
1307 parameter was relatively low. However, when using this algorithm in combination with an
1308 advanced signal processing method, such as ICA, PCA or WT, the elimination of interfer-
1309 ence was more efficient and the extraction of the useful signal was successful. Unfortunately,
1310 the limitation of AI-based algorithms, in particular ANNs, included the dependence of the
1311 high quality extraction on the appropriate setting of a large number of network hyperparam-
1312 eters. If the network hyperparameters were set inappropriately, the resulting efficiency of the
1313 algorithm was significantly reduced. To ensure the optimal setting of ANNs hyperparame-
1314 ters, it would be appropriate to combine these methods with nature-inspired optimization
1315 techniques. These nature-inspired optimization approaches have proved to be very effective
1316 especially in finding the optimal ANC filter settings. On the other hand, the use of older op-
1317 timization algorithms, such as PSO, can lead to an overall higher computational complexity
1318 of the method. Therefore, in future research, it would be appropriate to implement more
1319 recent optimization methods, such as salp swarm algorithm [190] or planet optimization
1320 algorithm [191], to achieve both optimal settings and low computational complexity.

1321 The use of BCIs for communication purposes is one of the important areas that allows
1322 severely disabled patients to communicate with the outside world. Based on the results
1323 obtained in the individual studies, comparable performance was shown for both the more
1324 computationally demanding CNN and the simpler SVM and LDA classifiers, as seen in Table
1325 3. Lower accuracy was generally achieved in disabled patients compared to healthy subjects,
1326 which could probably be due to the need for a longer training time for disabled subjects. An
1327 increase in classification accuracy could also be achieved by using stimuli that may evoke
1328 higher ERPs, such as 3-D or VM stimuli. Similarly, as in [142], it was further proved that
1329 the users were more frustrated by typos than by a slow-running system. It would, therefore,
1330 be useful to design an automatic and user-friendly error correction system.

1331 Passive BCI systems have proved promising in estimating cognitive and affective states.
1332 However, compared to the results of ACC values obtained in the field of communication
1333 and motor imagery, the average values of classification accuracy under mental condition
1334 estimation were lower. This could be due to the fact that, in the case of passive BCIs,
1335 spontaneous brain activity was analyzed (as opposed to active or reactive BCIs). The
1336 analysis and interpretation of these higher order information were thus more demanding for
1337 both AI- and ML-based algorithms leading to the resulting lower performance, see Table
1338 4. In addition, in most cases, only two classification classes were used for the classification,
1339 which may not be sufficient for use in real conditions (for example, in estimating emotions
1340 that are numerous). Therefore, during further experiments, it would be useful to test the
1341 multi-class classification. In addition, experiments should be conducted in daily real life

1342 scenarios in which the signals have a lower amplitude, and the efficiency of the algorithms
1343 may be even lower.

1344 Similar to noise cancellation, also in the field of MI it turned out, when using a single
1345 algorithm based on AI or ML, the resulting accuracy was not sufficient in most cases, as could
1346 be seen in Table 5. When these algorithms were combined with other methods, the value
1347 of ACC was increased, while the complexity of the system was reduced. The combination
1348 of AI or ML algorithms with advanced signal processing methods (e.g. PCA, EMD, VMD
1349 and WT) for feature extraction or nature-inspired techniques, such as GA or GWO for
1350 optimal feature subset selection, has proved to be suitable. Since a decreasing accuracy
1351 was observed for the four-class compared to the two-class classification, it is, therefore,
1352 necessary to increase the accuracy for the multi-class classification as well. In addition, in
1353 a large number of studies, algorithms have only been tested on dataset signals, which may
1354 not fully reflect the effectiveness of the methods in real-time applications. In the future,
1355 it would, therefore, be very beneficial to test algorithms for online control of a real device,
1356 where it is essential to have a fast and accurate solution.

1357 The most significant challenge in designing a robust model for processing, analyzing, or
1358 interpreting the brain signals remains the non-stationary and non-linear nature of the input
1359 signals. This is also the main reason that traditional algorithms fail to solve these complex
1360 tasks, while AI and ML-based algorithms have generally been able to cope with this obstacle
1361 and provide satisfactory results. Nevertheless, it is important to note that not all AI and
1362 ML-based algorithms have shown to be equally efficient and the differences between them
1363 have been reported. According to the literature survey, the most preferred methods were
1364 ANNs, especially CNN, LSTM and ELM, as they were able to effectively learn the non-linear
1365 and non-stationary nature of a time series and excelled in their high generalization ability.
1366 Similarly, the methods using the fuzzy logic proved to be effective for this task as they are
1367 able to work with the uncertainty and inaccuracy of the data.

1368 In contrast, the processing of non-linear and non-stationary signals appeared as problem-
1369 atic for linear ML-based methods such as LDA or SRDA. On the other hand, the non-linear
1370 ML-based methods, such as SVM or KNN, stood out with very good predictability and
1371 delivered satisfactory results. Finally, it is worth noting that for most of the methods, the
1372 performance can be further improved by using more training data.

1373 *4.2. Remaining Challenges*

1374 As it has been shown, the processing and analysis of brain signals is a relatively demand-
1375 ing and complex area in which there is still room for improvement and further development.
1376 The main factors that affect the performance of the individual algorithms include the quality
1377 of input signals. If poor quality signals are used (e.g. with a high level of interference and a
1378 low level of the useful signal, or signals with missing sections or outliers), unnecessary loss
1379 of significant information and reduced accuracy in brain signal analysis may occur. Since
1380 many channels are usually used when recording brain signals, it is advisable to select only
1381 those with the highest quality and to exclude those of lower quality. Therefore, it would
1382 be appropriate to focus further research on the design of AI- or ML-based algorithms for
1383 the automated selection of high-quality input signals, as proposed by Kim et al. [192]. The

1384 authors experimentally verified the use of binary PSO for optimal channel selection in EEG-
1385 based BCI and achieved higher classification accuracy using only some channels than using
1386 all available channels.

1387 Another way to increase the performance of BCI systems is to design so-called *hybrid*
1388 multimodal BCIs, which combine two measurement techniques, such as EEG and fNIRS
1389 [193, 194, 195, 196], EEG and MEG [197, 198] or EEG a fMRI [199, 200]. By combining
1390 these approaches, it is possible to obtain diverse brain activity patterns, thus extracting more
1391 clinical information and increasing the overall performance of the BCI system compared
1392 to using one technique alone. The challenge and thus the subject of further research in
1393 these complex systems may include the issue of synchronization and specific processing and
1394 analysis of the recorded signals.

1395 The training process of AI- and ML-based approaches is another important factor in-
1396 fluencing the performance of these algorithms in the subsequent testing phase. In order
1397 for training to be as effective as possible, it is necessary to have an extensive and diverse
1398 dataset, the so-called Big Data. However, this type of dataset is only available for EEG (e.g.
1399 on the UCI Machine Learning Repository [201]). In the case of fNIRS, MEG, and fMRI,
1400 the number of any publicly available data-sets is significantly reduced, and, as far as Big
1401 Data is concerned, none are available with these techniques. This is probably due to the
1402 complexity and financial cost of recording. The same applies to ECoG and iCor, where the
1403 invasiveness of the measurement is the main obstacle. Hence, for further research, it would
1404 be very beneficial to create a unified, large dataset for all measuring techniques, containing
1405 both physiological and pathological data with a reference classification class determined by
1406 experts. Creating a dataset with synthetic signals, as in the case [202], where the authors
1407 dealt with the generation of EEG signals, is also a possible alternative. However, these
1408 synthetic signals may not accurately reflect the characteristics of the real signals, and the
1409 performance of the algorithms may vary. It would also be beneficial to introduce a uniform
1410 methodology for interpreting the effectiveness of classification algorithms.

1411 Although AI and ML-based algorithms provide relatively high effectiveness and mul-
1412 tifunctionality, they still face the non-linear, non-stationary, and chaotic nature of brain
1413 signals, especially during real-time processing. This issue thus remains a challenge for fu-
1414 ture research. A possible solution to increase the accuracy and reliability of BCI systems
1415 could be the implementation of deep learning models. Currently, there is limited develop-
1416 ment of deep learning models that consider the impact of non-linearity and non-stationarity
1417 of brain signals. The improvement of deep learning along with the use of Big Data could
1418 thus lead to excellent results in the future. On the other hand, their time-consuming nature
1419 can be an obstacle to implementation within a real-time device. In addition, the need to
1420 use Big Data to improve the performance of the AI- or ML-based algorithm exacerbates
1421 this time-consuming. Parallel processing could be a potential solution, as it allows dealing
1422 with many calculations simultaneously, thus significantly reducing the computational cost,
1423 as shown in [203].

1424 5. Conclusion

1425 The findings in this review showed that AI- and ML-based algorithms are a very promis-
1426 ing solution for processing and analysis of brain signals, both in the case of conventional
1427 EEG-based BCIs and in the case of alternative BCI systems based on the measurement of
1428 fNIRS, MEG, fMRI, ECoG and iCor signals. Five main application areas were mentioned,
1429 which have received the most attention in recent years. The first one was devoted to cali-
1430 bration, where it was desirable to design a rapid calibration system or calibration-free BCI
1431 to reduce the calibration time. The second one was focused on interference suppression, es-
1432 pecially for EEG signals, which have very low amplitudes and are also disturbed by various
1433 types of wide spectral artifacts. The remaining three areas focused on practical classification
1434 issues within communication, mental condition estimation and MI.

1435 Although the results of a number of AI- and ML-based algorithms were mentioned,
1436 their objective comparison was almost impossible due to the different methodologies and
1437 datasets/subjects used in the individual studies. Therefore, for future research, it would be
1438 appropriate to create high-quality Big Data data-sets for all measurement techniques con-
1439 taining a variety of both physiological and pathological recordings and a unified methodology
1440 for evaluating the effectiveness of classification algorithms. According to the subjective eval-
1441 uation, the use of ANNs, especially CNNs, seemed to be a universal approach suitable for
1442 all the application areas mentioned. The main disadvantages of these networks are the high
1443 computational complexity and dependence of the efficiency of algorithms on the appropriate
1444 setting of a large number of hyperparameters. Finding the optimal settings and reducing
1445 computational complexity could be achieved by a combination of ANN and nature-inspired
1446 optimization techniques, the implementation of which has also proved successful with ANC
1447 filters. As for ML-based algorithms, LDA and SVM methods seemed to be the most promis-
1448 ing. Compared to CNNs, the performance of these methods was slightly lower, but low
1449 computational complexity was their advantage. Performance improvement was achieved by
1450 combining ML methods with advanced signal processing algorithms such as WT, EMD, ICA
1451 or PCA for reducing dimensionality or feature extraction.

1452 However, for all algorithms in all application domains, a significantly decreasing accuracy
1453 was observed when testing in disabled patients compared to healthy subjects, and further
1454 improvement is thus necessary for these subjects. There is also a need to test methods
1455 using a larger number of classification classes and in daily life scenarios. An increase in
1456 classification accuracy could be achieved by using AI- and ML-based algorithms for optimal
1457 channel selection or by designing hybrid BCIs combining two measurement techniques. To
1458 reduce the computational cost and enable the real-time application of these techniques, the
1459 possibility of using parallel processing should also be explored.

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1470 References

- 1471 [1] S. N. Abdulkader, A. Atia, M.-S. M. Mostafa, Brain computer interfacing, *Egyptian Informatics*
1472 *Journal* 16 (2) (2015) 213–230. doi:10.1016/j.eij.2015.06.002.
1473 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1110866515000237>
- 1474 [2] A. Kawala-Sterniuk, N. Browarska, A. Al-Bakri, M. Pelc, J. Zygarlicki, M. Sidikova, R. Martinek, E. J.
1475 Gorzelanczyk, Summary of over fifty years with brain-computer interfaces—a review, *Brain Sciences*
1476 11 (1) (2021). doi:10.3390/brainsci11010043.
1477 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3425/11/1/43>
- 1478 [3] M.-P. Hosseini, D. Pompili, K. Elisevich, H. Soltanian-Zadeh, Optimized deep learning for eeg big data
1479 and seizure prediction bci via internet of things, *IEEE Transactions on Big Data* 3 (4) (2017-12-1)
1480 392–404. doi:10.1109/TBDATA.2017.2769670.
1481 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8094871/>
- 1482 [4] M. Bamdad, H. Zarshenas, M. A. Auais, Application of bci systems in neurorehabilitation, *Disability*
1483 *and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology* 10 (5) (2015-01-05) 355–364. doi:10.3109/17483107.2014.
1484 961569.
1485 URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.3109/17483107.2014.961569>
- 1486 [5] W. Karwowski, W. Siemionow, K. Gielo-Periczak, Physical neuroergonomics: The human brain in
1487 control of physical work activities, *Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science* 4 (1-2) (2003) 175–199.
- 1488 [6] E. P. Torres, E. A. Torres, M. Hernández-Álvarez, S. G. Yoo, Eeg-based bci emotion recognition,
1489 *Sensors* 20 (18) (2020) 1–36. doi:10.3390/s20185083.
1490 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/20/18/5083>
- 1491 [7] X. Zhang, J. Li, Y. Liu, Z. Zhang, Z. Wang, D. Luo, X. Zhou, M. Zhu, W. Salman, G. Hu, C. Wang,
1492 Design of a fatigue detection system for high-speed trains based on driver vigilance using a wireless
1493 wearable eeg, *Sensors* 17 (3) (2017) 1–21. doi:10.3390/s17030486.
1494 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/3/486>
- 1495 [8] A. Kübler, The history of bci, *Neuroethics* 13 (2) (2020) 163–180. doi:10.1007/
1496 s12152-019-09409-4.
1497 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s12152-019-09409-4>
- 1498 [9] A. Jackson, C. T. Moritz, J. Mavoori, T. H. Lucas, E. E. Fetz, The neurochip bci: towards a neural
1499 prosthesis for upper limb function, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engi-*
1500 *neering* 14 (2) (2006) 187–190.
- 1501 [10] A. F. Al-Bakri, R. Martinek, M. Pelc, J. Zygarlicki, A. Kawala-Sterniuk, Implementation of a mor-
1502 phological filter for removing spikes from the epileptic brain signals to improve identification ripples,
1503 *Sensors* 22 (19) (2022) 7522.
- 1504 [11] C. Eastmond, A. Subedi, S. De, X. Intes, Deep learning in fnirs: a review, *Neurophotonics* 9 (4) (2022)
1505 041411.
- 1506 [12] J. J. Shih, D. J. Krusienski, J. R. Wolpaw, Brain-computer interfaces in medicine, *Mayo Clinic Pro-*
1507 *ceedings* 87 (3) (2012) 268–279. doi:10.1016/j.mayocp.2011.12.008.
1508 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0025619612001231>
- 1509 [13] R. Mane, Z. Wu, D. Wang, Poststroke motor, cognitive and speech rehabilitation with brain-computer
1510 interface: a perspective review, *Stroke and Vascular Neurology* 7 (6) (2022).
- 1511 [14] A. Palumbo, Microsoft hololens 2 in medical and healthcare context: state of the art and future
1512 prospects, *Sensors* 22 (20) (2022) 7709.

- 1513 [15] R. Martinek, M. Ladrova, M. Sidikova, R. Jaros, K. Behbehani, R. Kahankova, A. Kawala-Sterniuk,
 1514 Advanced bioelectrical signal processing methods, *Sensors* 21 (19) (2021). doi:10.3390/s21196343.
 1515 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/21/19/6343>
- 1516 [16] S. N. S. S. Daud, R. Sudirman, Wavelet based filters for artifact elimination in electroencephalography
 1517 signal: A review, *Annals of Biomedical Engineering* 50 (10) (2022) 1271–1291.
- 1518 [17] J. Yu, C. Li, K. Lou, C. Wei, Q. Liu, Embedding decomposition for artifacts removal in eeg signals,
 1519 *Journal of Neural Engineering* 19 (2) (2022) 026052.
- 1520 [18] O.-Y. Kwon, M.-H. Lee, C. Guan, S.-W. Lee, Subject-independent brain–computer interfaces based
 1521 on deep convolutional neural networks, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*
 1522 31 (10) (2020) 3839–3852. doi:10.1109/TNNLS.2019.2946869.
 1523 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8897723/>
- 1524 [19] M. S. H. Sunny, S. Hossain, N. Afroze, M. K. Hasan, E. Hossain, M. H. Rahman, Understanding the
 1525 nonlinear behavior of eeg with advanced machine learning in artifact elimination, *Biomedical Physics
 1526 & Engineering Express* 8 (1) (2021-12-09). doi:10.1088/2057-1976/ac3f17.
 1527 URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/2057-1976/ac3f17>
- 1528 [20] S. Olsen, J. Zhang, K.-F. Liang, M. Lam, U. Riaz, J. C. Kao, An artificial intelligence that increases
 1529 simulated brain–computer interface performance, *Journal of Neural Engineering* 18 (4) (2021-05-13).
 1530 doi:10.1088/1741-2552/abfaaa.
 1531 URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1741-2552/abfaaa>
- 1532 [21] H. Huang, Q. Xie, J. Pan, Y. He, Z. Wen, R. Yu, Y. Li, An eeg-based brain computer interface for
 1533 emotion recognition and its application in patients with disorder of consciousness, *IEEE Transactions
 1534 on Affective Computing* 12 (4) (2021-10-1) 832–842. doi:10.1109/TAFFC.2019.2901456.
 1535 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8651389/>
- 1536 [22] K. Li, S. Ramkumar, J. Thimmiaraja, S. Diwakaran, Optimized artificial neural network based perfor-
 1537 mance analysis of wheelchair movement for als patients, *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine* 102 (2020)
 1538 1–11. doi:10.1016/j.artmed.2019.101754.
 1539 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0933365719308991>
- 1540 [23] H. Khan, F. M. Noori, A. Yazidi, M. Z. Uddin, M. N. A. Khan, P. Mirtaheri, Classification of
 1541 individual finger movements from right hand using fnirs signals, *Sensors* 21 (23) (2021) 1–15. doi:
 1542 10.3390/s21237943.
 1543 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/21/23/7943>
- 1544 [24] H. Kim, H. Hwang, Application of artificial intelligence (ai) and machine learning (ml) in pediatric
 1545 epilepsy: a narrative review, *Pediatric Medicine* 5 (2022) 6399.
- 1546 [25] F.-M. Toma, A hybrid neuro-experimental decision support system to classify overconfidence and
 1547 performance in a simulated bubble using a passive bci, *Expert Systems with Applications* 212 (2023)
 1548 118722.
- 1549 [26] Y. Ma, A. Gong, W. Nan, P. Ding, F. Wang, Y. Fu, Personalized brain–computer interface and its
 1550 applications, *Journal of Personalized Medicine* 13 (1) (2023) 46.
- 1551 [27] F. Lotte, L. Bougrain, M. Clerc, *Electroencephalography (eeg)-based brain-computer interfaces*, Wiley
 1552 *Encyclopedia of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*, Wiley (2015) 1–44doi:10.1002/047134608X.
 1553 W8278.
 1554 URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/047134608X.W8278>
- 1555 [28] A. Bablani, D. R. Edla, R. Cheruku, Survey on brain-computer interface: An emerging computational
 1556 intelligence paradigm, *ACM Computing Surveys* 52 (1) (2019) 1–32. doi:10.1145/3297713.
 1557 URL <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3297713>
- 1558 [29] Y. Chae, J. Jeong, S. Jo, Toward brain-actuated humanoid robots: asynchronous direct control using
 1559 an eeg-based bci, *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* 28 (5) (2012) 1131–1144.
- 1560 [30] X. Gu, Z. Cao, A. Jolfaei, P. Xu, D. Wu, T.-P. Jung, C.-T. Lin, Eeg-based brain-computer interfaces
 1561 (bcis), *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics* 18 (5) (2021-9-1)
 1562 1645–1666. doi:10.1109/TCBB.2021.3052811.
 1563 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9328561/>

- 1564 [31] M. Ahn, M. Lee, J. Choi, S. Jun, A review of brain-computer interface games and an opinion survey
1565 from researchers, developers and users, *Sensors* 14 (8) (2014) 14601–14633. doi:10.3390/s140814601.
1566 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/14/8/14601>
- 1567 [32] A. Appriou, A. Cichocki, F. Lotte, Modern machine-learning algorithms, *IEEE Systems, Man, and*
1568 *Cybernetics Magazine* 6 (3) (2020) 29–38. doi:10.1109/MSMC.2020.2968638.
1569 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9141493/>
- 1570 [33] A. Kumari, D. R. Edla, A study on brain-computer interface: Methods and applications, *SN Computer*
1571 *Science* 4 (2) (2023) 1–7.
- 1572 [34] H. Alharbi, et al., Identifying thematic in a brain-computer interface research, *Computational Intel-*
1573 *ligence and Neuroscience* 2023 (2023).
- 1574 [35] A. Kawala-Sterniuk, M. Podpora, M. Pelc, M. Blaszczyszyn, E. J. Gorzelanczyk, R. Martinek,
1575 S. Ozana, Comparison of smoothing filters in analysis of eeg data for the medical diagnostics pur-
1576 poses, *Sensors* 20 (3) (2020) 807.
- 1577 [36] K. Värbu, N. Muhammad, Y. Muhammad, Past, present, and future of eeg-based bci applications,
1578 *Sensors* 22 (9) (2022) 3331.
- 1579 [37] A. Biasiucci, B. Franceschiello, M. M. Murray, *Electroencephalography*, *Current Biology* 29 (3) (2019)
1580 R80–R85. doi:10.1016/j.cub.2018.11.052.
1581 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0960982218315513>
- 1582 [38] J. Minguillon, M. A. Lopez-Gordo, F. Pelayo, Trends in eeg-bci for daily-life: Requirements for artifact
1583 removal, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 31 (2017) 407–418.
- 1584 [39] X. Jiang, G.-B. Bian, Z. Tian, Removal of artifacts from eeg signals, *Sensors* 19 (5) (2019) 1–18.
1585 doi:10.3390/s19050987.
1586 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/19/5/987>
- 1587 [40] C. Rashmi, C. Shantala, Eeg artifacts detection and removal techniques for brain computer interface
1588 applications: a systematic review, *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering*
1589 *Exploration* 9 (88) (2022) 354.
- 1590 [41] M. Proudfoot, M. W. Woolrich, A. C. Nobre, M. R. Turner, *Magnetoencephalography*, *Practical*
1591 *Neurology* 14 (5) (2014-09-09) 336–343. doi:10.1136/practneuro1-2013-000768.
1592 URL <http://pn.bmj.com/lookup/doi/10.1136/practneuro1-2013-000768>
- 1593 [42] B. S. Philip, G. Prasad, D. J. Hemanth, Non-stationarity removal techniques in meg data: A review,
1594 *Procedia Computer Science* 215 (2022) 824–833.
- 1595 [43] H. Xu, A. Gong, P. Ding, J. Luo, C. Chen, Y. Fu, Key technologies for intelligent brain-computer
1596 interaction based on magnetoencephalography, *Sheng wu yi xue Gong Cheng xue za zhi= Journal of*
1597 *Biomedical Engineering= Shengwu Yixue Gongchengxue Zazhi* 39 (1) (2022) 198–206.
- 1598 [44] S. Singh, *Magnetoencephalography*, *Annals of Indian Academy of Neurology* 17 (5) (2014) S107–S112.
1599 doi:10.4103/0972-2327.128676.
1600 URL <http://www.annalsofian.org/text.asp?2014/17/5/107/128676>
- 1601 [45] L. F. Nicolas-Alonso, J. Gomez-Gil, Brain computer interfaces, a review, *Sensors* 12 (2) (2012) 1211–
1602 1279. doi:10.3390/s120201211.
1603 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/12/2/1211>
- 1604 [46] T. Rocha, D. Carvalho, P. Letra, A. Reis, J. Barroso, Bci: Technologies and applications review
1605 and toolkit proposal, in: *Multimedia Communications, Services and Security: 11th International*
1606 *Conference, MCSS 2022, Kraków, Poland, November 3–4, 2022, Proceedings*, Springer, 2022, pp.
1607 126–143.
- 1608 [47] T. M. Tierney, N. Holmes, S. Mellor, J. D. López, G. Roberts, R. M. Hill, E. Boto, J. Leggett, V. Shah,
1609 M. J. Brookes, R. Bowtell, G. R. Barnes, Optically pumped magnetometers, *NeuroImage* 199 (2019)
1610 598–608. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2019.05.063.
1611 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1053811919304550>
- 1612 [48] J. Len-Carrin, U. Len-Domnguez, Functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fnirs), in: *Neuroimaging -*
1613 *Methods*, InTech, 2012-02-17. doi:10.5772/23146.
1614 URL <http://www.intechopen.com/books/neuroimaging-methods/functional-near-infrared-spectroscopy-1>

- 1615 [49] A. Kassab, J. L. Lan, P. Vannasing, M. Sawan, Functional near-infrared spectroscopy caps for brain
1616 activity monitoring, *Applied Optics* 54 (3) (2015) 576–586. doi:10.1364/AO.54.000576.
1617 URL <https://opg.optica.org/abstract.cfm?URI=ao-54-3-576>
- 1618 [50] M. Abtahi, G. Cay, M. J. Saikia, K. Mankodiya, Designing and testing a wearable, wireless fnirs
1619 patch, in: 2016 38th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and
1620 Biology Society (EMBC), IEEE, 2016, pp. 6298–6301.
- 1621 [51] F. Lange, I. Tachtsidis, Clinical brain monitoring with time domain nirs: a review and future perspec-
1622 tives, *Applied Sciences* 9 (8) (2019) 1612.
- 1623 [52] S. Hosni, S. Borgheai, J. McLinden, Y. Shahriari, An fnirs-based motor imagery bci for als: A subject-
1624 specific data-driven approach, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*
1625 28 (12) (2020) 3063–3073.
- 1626 [53] Y. Tong, J. F. Yao, J. J. Chen, B. deB Frederick, The resting-state fmri arterial signal predicts
1627 differential blood transit time through the brain, *Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow & Metabolism*
1628 39 (6) (2019) 1148–1160. doi:10.1177/0271678X17753329.
1629 URL <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0271678X17753329>
- 1630 [54] T. Skok, P. Tabakow, K. Chmielak, Methods of integrating the human nervous system with electronic
1631 circuits, *Adv. Clin. Exp. Med* 28 (2019) 1125–1135.
- 1632 [55] B. Sorger, R. Goebel, Real-time fmri for brain-computer interfacing, *Handbook of clinical neurology*
1633 168 (2020) 289–302.
- 1634 [56] Z.-P. Zhao, C. Nie, C.-T. Jiang, S.-H. Cao, K.-X. Tian, S. Yu, J.-W. Gu, Modulating brain activity
1635 with invasive brain-computer interface: A narrative review, *Brain Sciences* 13 (1) (2023) 134.
- 1636 [57] N. Even-Chen, D. G. Muratore, S. D. Stavisky, L. R. Hochberg, J. M. Henderson, B. Murmann, K. V.
1637 Shenoy, Power-saving design opportunities for wireless intracortical brain-computer interfaces, *Nature*
1638 *Biomedical Engineering* 4 (10) (2020) 984–996. doi:10.1038/s41551-020-0595-9.
1639 URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41551-020-0595-9>
- 1640 [58] K. Xu, S. Li, S. Dong, S. Zhang, G. Pan, G. Wang, L. Shi, W. Guo, C. Yu, J. Luo, Bioresorbable
1641 electrode array for electrophysiological and pressure signal recording in the brain, *Advanced Healthcare*
1642 *Materials* 8 (15) (2019-06-14). doi:10.1002/adhm.201801649.
1643 URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/adhm.201801649>
- 1644 [59] T. Yang, S. Hakimian, T. H. Schwartz, Intraoperative electrocorticography (ecog), *Epileptic Disorders*
1645 16 (3) (2014) 271–279. doi:10.1684/epd.2014.0675.
1646 URL <http://www.john-libbey-eurotext.fr/medline.md?doi=10.1684/epd.2014.0675>
- 1647 [60] D. M. Brandman, T. Hosman, J. Saab, M. C. Burkhart, B. E. Shanahan, J. G. Ciancibello, A. A.
1648 Sarma, D. J. Milstein, C. E. Vargas-Irwin, B. Franco, J. Kelemen, C. Blabe, B. A. Murphy, D. R.
1649 Young, F. R. Willett, C. Pandarinath, S. D. Stavisky, R. F. Kirsch, B. L. Walter, A. B. Ajiboye,
1650 S. S. Cash, E. N. Eskandar, J. P. Miller, J. A. Sweet, K. V. Shenoy, J. M. Henderson, B. Jarosiewicz,
1651 M. T. Harrison, J. D. Simeral, L. R. Hochberg, Rapid calibration of an intracortical brain-computer
1652 interface for people with tetraplegia, *Journal of Neural Engineering* 15 (2) (2018-04-01) 1–26. doi:
1653 10.1088/1741-2552/aa9ee7.
1654 URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1741-2552/aa9ee7>
- 1655 [61] D. Wu, Online and offline domain adaptation for reducing bci calibration effort, *IEEE Transactions*
1656 *on Human-Machine Systems* 47 (4) (2017) 550–563. doi:10.1109/THMS.2016.2608931.
1657 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7580614/>
- 1658 [62] J. Jin, S. Li, I. Daly, Y. Miao, C. Liu, X. Wang, A. Cichocki, The study of generic model set for reducing
1659 calibration time in p300-based brain-computer interface, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and*
1660 *Rehabilitation Engineering* 28 (1) (2020) 3–12. doi:10.1109/TNSRE.2019.2956488.
1661 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8917686/>
- 1662 [63] J. Faller, R. Scherer, U. Costa, E. Opisso, J. Medina, G. R. Müller-Putz, D. Friedman, A co-adaptive
1663 brain-computer interface for end users with severe motor impairment, *PLoS ONE* 9 (7) (2014-7-11).
1664 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0101168.
1665 URL <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0101168>

- 1666 [64] B. Jarosiewicz, A. A. Sarma, J. Saab, B. Franco, S. S. Cash, E. N. Eskandar, L. R. Hochberg,
1667 Retrospectively supervised click decoder calibration for self-calibrating point-and-click brain-computer
1668 interfaces, *Journal of Physiology-Paris* 110 (4) (2016) 382–391. doi:10.1016/j.jphysparis.2017.
1669 03.001.
1670 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0928425717300104>
- 1671 [65] X. Zhu, P. Li, C. Li, D. Yao, R. Zhang, P. Xu, Separated channel convolutional neural network to
1672 realize the training free motor imagery bci systems, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 49
1673 (2019) 396–403. doi:10.1016/j.bspc.2018.12.027.
1674 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1746809418303264>
- 1675 [66] J. Lee, K. Won, M. Kwon, S. C. Jun, M. Ahn, Cnn with large data achieves true zero-training in
1676 online p300 brain-computer interface, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 74385–74400. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.
1677 2020.2988057.
1678 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9068248/>
- 1679 [67] W. Gao, T. Yu, J.-G. Yu, Z. Gu, K. Li, Y. Huang, Z. L. Yu, Y. Li, Learning invariant patterns based
1680 on a convolutional neural network and big electroencephalography data for subject-independent p300
1681 brain-computer interfaces, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering* 29
1682 (2021) 1047–1057. doi:10.1109/TNSRE.2021.3083548.
1683 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9440400/>
- 1684 [68] B. Yang, K. Duan, C. Fan, C. Hu, J. Wang, Automatic ocular artifacts removal in eeg using deep
1685 learning, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 43 (2018) 148–158. doi:10.1016/j.bspc.2018.
1686 02.021.
1687 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1746809418300521>
- 1688 [69] V. Gandhi, G. Prasad, D. Coyle, L. Behera, T. M. McGinnity, Quantum neural network-based eeg
1689 filtering for a brain-computer interface, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*
1690 25 (2) (2014) 278–288. doi:10.1109/TNNLS.2013.2274436.
1691 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6575167/>
- 1692 [70] H. Cecotti, A. Graser, Convolutional neural networks for p300 detection with application to brain-
1693 computer interfaces, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 33 (3) (2011)
1694 433–445. doi:10.1109/TPAMI.2010.125.
1695 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5492691/>
- 1696 [71] Z. Oralhan, A new paradigm for region-based p300 speller in brain computer interface, *IEEE Access*
1697 7 (2019) 106618–106627. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2933049.
1698 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8787846/>
- 1699 [72] J. Qu, F. Wang, Z. Xia, T. Yu, J. Xiao, Z. Yu, Z. Gu, Y. Li, A novel three-dimensional p300 speller
1700 based on stereo visual stimuli, *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems* 48 (4) (2018) 392–399.
1701 doi:10.1109/THMS.2018.2799525.
1702 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8288852/>
- 1703 [73] F. Akram, S. M. Han, T.-S. Kim, An efficient word typing p300-bci system using a modified t9
1704 interface and random forest classifier, *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 56 (2015) 30–36. doi:
1705 10.1016/j.combiomed.2014.10.021.
1706 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0010482514002959>
- 1707 [74] F. Cavrini, L. Bianchi, L. R. Quitadamo, G. Saggio, A fuzzy integral ensemble method in visual
1708 p300 brain-computer interface, *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience* 2016 (2016) 1–9. doi:
1709 10.1155/2016/9845980.
1710 URL <http://www.hindawi.com/journals/cin/2016/9845980/>
- 1711 [75] D. Bacher, B. Jarosiewicz, N. Y. Masse, S. D. Stavisky, J. D. Simeral, K. Newell, E. M. Oakley, S. S.
1712 Cash, G. Friehs, L. R. Hochberg, Neural point-and-click communication by a person with incomplete
1713 locked-in syndrome, *Neurorehabilitation and Neural Repair* 29 (5) (2015) 462–471. doi:10.1177/
1714 1545968314554624.
1715 URL <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1545968314554624>
- 1716 [76] N. Even-Chen, S. D. Stavisky, C. Pandarinath, P. Nuyujukian, C. B. Blabe, L. R. Hochberg, J. M.

- 1717 Henderson, K. V. Shenoy, Feasibility of automatic error detect-and-undo system in human intracortical
 1718 brain-computer interfaces, *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 65 (8) (2018) 1771–1784.
 1719 doi:10.1109/TBME.2017.2776204.
 1720 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8116673/>
- [77] A. J. Casson, Artificial neural network classification of operator workload with an assessment of time
 1721 variation and noise-enhancement to increase performance, *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 8 (2014-12-01)
 1722 1–10. doi:10.3389/fnins.2014.00372.
 1723 URL <http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnins.2014.00372/abstract>
- [78] U. Asgher, K. Khalil, M. J. Khan, R. Ahmad, S. I. Butt, Y. Ayaz, N. Naseer, S. Nazir, Enhanced
 1724 accuracy for multiclass mental workload detection using long short-term memory for brain-computer
 1725 interface, *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 14 (2020-6-23) 1–19. doi:10.3389/fnins.2020.00584.
 1726 URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnins.2020.00584/full>
- [79] M. Bagheri, S. D. Power, Simultaneous classification of both mental workload and stress level suitable
 1727 for an online passive brain-computer interface, *Sensors* 22 (2) (2022) 1–17. doi:10.3390/s22020535.
 1728 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/22/2/535>
- [80] T. Gateau, H. Ayaz, F. Dehais, In silico vs. over the clouds, *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience* 12
 1729 (2018-5-17) 1–14. doi:10.3389/fnhum.2018.00187.
 1730 URL <http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnhum.2018.00187/full>
- [81] M. A. Tanveer, M. J. Khan, M. J. Qureshi, N. Naseer, K.-S. Hong, Enhanced drowsiness detection
 1731 using deep learning, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 137920–137929. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2942838.
 1732 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8846024/>
- [82] Z. Gao, X. Wang, Y. Yang, C. Mu, Q. Cai, W. Dang, S. Zuo, Eeg-based spatio-temporal convolutional
 1733 neural network for driver fatigue evaluation, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning
 1734 Systems* 30 (9) (2019) 2755–2763. doi:10.1109/TNNLS.2018.2886414.
 1735 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8607897/>
- [83] R. Sánchez-Reolid, A. García, M. Vicente-Querol, L. Fernández-Aguilar, M. López, A. González,
 1736 Artificial neural networks to assess emotional states from brain-computer interface, *Electronics* 7 (12)
 1737 (2018) 1–12. doi:10.3390/electronics7120384.
 1738 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/7/12/384>
- [84] S. Jirayucharoensak, S. Pan-Ngum, P. Israsena, Eeg-based emotion recognition using deep learning
 1739 network with principal component based covariate shift adaptation, *The Scientific World Journal* 2014
 1740 (2014) 1–10. doi:10.1155/2014/627892.
 1741 URL <http://www.hindawi.com/journals/tswj/2014/627892/>
- [85] J. Atkinson, D. Campos, Improving bci-based emotion recognition by combining eeg feature selection
 1742 and kernel classifiers, *Expert Systems with Applications* 47 (2016) 35–41. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.
 1743 2015.10.049.
 1744 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0957417415007538>
- [86] J. Pan, Q. Xie, Y. He, F. Wang, H. Di, S. Laureys, R. Yu, Y. Li, Detecting awareness in patients with
 1745 disorders of consciousness using a hybrid brain-computer interface, *Journal of Neural Engineering*
 1746 11 (5) (2014-10-01) 1–11. doi:10.1088/1741-2560/11/5/056007.
 1747 URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1741-2560/11/5/056007>
- [87] M. Pahwa, M. Kusner, C. D. Hacker, D. T. Bundy, K. Q. Weinberger, E. C. Leuthardt, N. N.
 1748 Pouratian, Optimizing the detection of wakeful and sleep-like states for future electrocorticographic
 1749 brain computer interface applications, *PLOS ONE* 10 (11) (2015-11-12) 1–16. doi:10.1371/journal.
 1750 pone.0142947.
 1751 URL <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0142947>
- [88] C. Yaacoub, G. Mhanna, S. Rihana, A genetic-based feature selection approach in the identification
 1752 of left/right hand motor imagery for a brain-computer interface, *Brain Sciences* 7 (12) (2017) 1–15.
 1753 doi:10.3390/brainsci7010012.
 1754 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/2076-3425/7/1/12>
- [89] L. He, D. Hu, M. Wan, Y. Wen, K. M. von Deneen, M. Zhou, Common bayesian network for classifica-

- 1768 tion of eeg-based multiclass motor imagery bci, *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics:*
1769 *Systems* 46 (6) (2016) 843–854. doi:10.1109/TSMC.2015.2450680.
1770 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7167726/>
- 1771 [90] T. jian Luo, C. le Zhou, F. Chao, Exploring spatial-frequency-sequential relationships for mo-
1772 tor imagery classification with recurrent neural network, *BMC Bioinformatics* 19 (1) (2018) 1–18.
1773 doi:10.1186/s12859-018-2365-1.
1774 URL <https://bmcbioinformatics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12859-018-2365-1>
- 1775 [91] M. Z. Baig, N. Aslam, H. P. Shum, L. Zhang, Differential evolution algorithm as a tool for optimal
1776 feature subset selection in motor imagery eeg, *Expert Systems with Applications* 90 (2017) 184–195.
1777 doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2017.07.033.
1778 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0957417417305109>
- 1779 [92] L.-W. Ko, C.-T. Lin, Y.-C. Lu, H. Bustince, Y.-C. Chang, Y. Chang, J. Ferandez, Y.-K. Wang, J. A.
1780 Sanz, G. P. Dimuro, Multimodal fuzzy fusion for enhancing the motor-imagery-based brain computer
1781 interface, *IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine* 14 (1) (2019) 96–106. doi:10.1109/MCI.2018.
1782 2881647.
1783 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8610089/>
- 1784 [93] Y. Fu, R. Chen, A. Gong, Q. Qian, N. Ding, W. Zhang, L. Su, L. Zhao, J. Tang, Recognition
1785 of flexion and extension imagery involving the right and left arms based on deep belief network
1786 and functional near-infrared spectroscopy, *Journal of Healthcare Engineering* 2021 (2021-6-29) 1–11.
1787 doi:10.1155/2021/5533565.
1788 URL <https://www.hindawi.com/journals/jhe/2021/5533565/>
- 1789 [94] C. Ieracitano, N. Mammone, A. Hussain, F. C. Morabito, A novel explainable machine learning
1790 approach for eeg-based brain-computer interface systems, *Neural Computing and Applications* 1-14
1791 (2021). doi:10.1007/s00521-020-05624-w.
1792 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00521-020-05624-w>
- 1793 [95] M. A. Schwemmer, N. D. Skomrock, P. B. Sederberg, J. E. Ting, G. Sharma, M. A. Bock-
1794 brader, D. A. Friedenberg, Meeting brain–computer interface user performance expectations us-
1795 ing a deep neural network decoding framework, *Nature Medicine* 24 (11) (2018) 1669–1676. doi:
1796 10.1038/s41591-018-0171-y.
1797 URL <http://www.nature.com/articles/s41591-018-0171-y>
- 1798 [96] D. Kuhner, L. Fiederer, J. Aldinger, F. Burget, M. Völker, R. Schirrmeister, C. Do, J. Boedecker,
1799 B. Nebel, T. Ball, W. Burgard, A service assistant combining autonomous robotics, flexible goal
1800 formulation, and deep-learning-based brain–computer interfacing, *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*
1801 116 (2019) 98–113. doi:10.1016/j.robot.2019.02.015.
1802 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0921889018302227>
- 1803 [97] M. Aljalal, R. Djemal, S. Ibrahim, Robot navigation using a brain computer interface based on
1804 motor imagery, *Journal of Medical and Biological Engineering* 39 (4) (2019) 508–522. doi:10.1007/
1805 s40846-018-0431-9.
1806 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s40846-018-0431-9>
- 1807 [98] A. M. Batula, Y. E. Kim, H. Ayaz, Virtual and actual humanoid robot control with four-class motor-
1808 imagery-based optical brain-computer interface, *BioMed Research International* 2017 (2017) 1–13.
1809 doi:10.1155/2017/1463512.
1810 URL <https://www.hindawi.com/journals/bmri/2017/1463512/>
- 1811 [99] L. Minati, A. Nigri, C. Rosazza, M. G. Bruzzone, Thoughts turned into high-level commands, *Medical*
1812 *Engineering & Physics* 34 (5) (2012) 650–658. doi:10.1016/j.medengphy.2012.02.004.
1813 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1350453312000288>
- 1814 [100] S.-L. Wu, Y.-T. Liu, T.-Y. Hsieh, Y.-Y. Lin, C.-Y. Chen, C.-H. Chuang, C.-T. Lin, Fuzzy integral with
1815 particle swarm optimization for a motor-imagery-based brain–computer interface, *IEEE Transactions*
1816 *on Fuzzy Systems* 25 (1) (2017) 21–28. doi:10.1109/TFUZZ.2016.2598362.
1817 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7542168/>
- 1818 [101] C. Wang, X. Wu, Z. Wang, Y. Ma, Implementation of a brain-computer interface on a lower-limb

- 1819 exoskeleton, *IEEE Access* 6 (2018) 38524–38534. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2853628.
 1820 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8405532/>
- 1821 [102] U. Asgher, M. J. Khan, M. H. A. Nizami, K. Khalil, R. Ahmad, Y. Ayaz, N. Naseer, Motor training
 1822 using mental workload (mwl) with an assistive soft exoskeleton system, *Frontiers in Neurorobotics* 15
 1823 (2021-3-18) 1–20. doi:10.3389/fnbot.2021.605751.
 1824 URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnbot.2021.605751/full>
- 1825 [103] A. Colucci, M. Vermehren, A. Cavallo, C. Angerhöfer, N. Peekhaus, L. Zollo, W.-S. Kim, N.-J.
 1826 Paik, S. R. Soekadar, Brain–computer interface-controlled exoskeletons in clinical neurorehabilitation:
 1827 Ready or not?, *Neurorehabilitation and Neural Repair* 36 (12) (2022) 747–756.
- 1828 [104] R. Zhang, Y. Li, Y. Yan, H. Zhang, S. Wu, T. Yu, Z. Gu, Control of a wheelchair in an indoor
 1829 environment based on a brain–computer interface and automated navigation, *IEEE Transactions on*
 1830 *Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering* 24 (1) (2016) 128–139. doi:10.1109/TNSRE.2015.
 1831 2439298.
 1832 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7115145/>
- 1833 [105] X. an Fan, L. Bi, T. Teng, H. Ding, Y. Liu, A brain–computer interface-based vehicle destination se-
 1834 lection system using p300 and ssvep signals, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*
 1835 16 (1) (2015) 274–283. doi:10.1109/TITS.2014.2330000.
 1836 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6847229>
- 1837 [106] A. Dhillon, G. K. Verma, Convolutional neural network, *Progress in Artificial Intelligence* 9 (2) (2020)
 1838 85–112. doi:10.1007/s13748-019-00203-0.
 1839 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s13748-019-00203-0>
- 1840 [107] J. Lu, V. Behbood, P. Hao, H. Zuo, S. Xue, G. Zhang, Transfer learning using computational intelli-
 1841 gence, *Knowledge-Based Systems* 80 (2015) 14–23. doi:10.1016/j.knosys.2015.01.010.
 1842 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0950705115000179>
- 1843 [108] J. S. García-Salinas, L. Villaseñor-Pineda, C. A. Reyes-García, A. A. Torres-García, Transfer learning
 1844 in imagined speech eeg-based bcis, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 50 (2019) 151–157.
 1845 doi:10.1016/j.bspc.2019.01.006.
 1846 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1746809419300060>
- 1847 [109] S. Wang, J. Lu, X. Gu, H. Du, J. Yang, Semi-supervised linear discriminant analysis for dimension
 1848 reduction and classification, *Pattern Recognition* 57 (2016) 179–189. doi:10.1016/j.patcog.2016.
 1849 02.019.
 1850 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S003132031600090X>
- 1851 [110] L. Hewing, J. Kabzan, M. N. Zeilinger, Cautious model predictive control using gaussian process
 1852 regression, *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology* 28 (6) (2020) 2736–2743. doi:10.
 1853 1109/TCST.2019.2949757.
 1854 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8909368/>
- 1855 [111] F. Nielsen, Hierarchical clustering, in: *Introduction to HPC with MPI for Data Science*, Springer
 1856 International Publishing, Cham, 2016, pp. 195–211. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-21903-5_8.
 1857 URL http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-21903-5_8
- 1858 [112] C.-S. Wei, Y.-P. Lin, Y.-T. Wang, C.-T. Lin, T.-P. Jung, A subject-transfer framework for obviating
 1859 inter- and intra-subject variability in eeg-based drowsiness detection, *NeuroImage* 174 (2018) 407–419.
 1860 doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.03.032.
 1861 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1053811918302428>
- 1862 [113] M. Tangermann, K.-R. Müller, A. Aertsen, N. Birbaumer, C. Braun, C. Brunner, R. Leeb, C. Mehring,
 1863 K. J. Miller, G. R. Müller-Putz, G. Nolte, G. Pfurtscheller, H. Preissl, G. Schalk, A. Schlögl, C. Vi-
 1864 daurre, S. Waldert, B. Blankertz, Review of the bci competition iv, *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 6 (2012).
 1865 doi:10.3389/fnins.2012.00055.
 1866 URL <http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnins.2012.00055/abstract>
- 1867 [114] C. Burger, D. J. van den Heever, Removal of eeg artefacts by combining wavelet neural network
 1868 and independent component analysis, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 15 (2015) 67–79.
 1869 doi:10.1016/j.bspc.2014.09.009.

- 1870 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S174680941400144X>
- 1871 [115] J. Hu, C. sheng Wang, M. Wu, Y. xiao Du, Y. He, J. She, Removal of eeg and emg artifacts from
1872 eeg using combination of functional link neural network and adaptive neural fuzzy inference system,
1873 *Neurocomputing* 151 (2015) 278–287. doi:10.1016/j.neucom.2014.09.040.
1874 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0925231214012259>
- 1875 [116] F. Lopes, A. Leal, J. Medeiros, M. F. Pinto, A. Dourado, M. Dumpelmann, C. Teixeira, Automatic
1876 electroencephalogram artifact removal using deep convolutional neural networks, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021)
1877 149955–149970. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3125728.
1878 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9605576/>
- 1879 [117] M. N. Anastasiadou, M. Christodoulakis, E. S. Papathanasiou, S. S. Papacostas, G. D. Mitsis, Un-
1880 supervised detection and removal of muscle artifacts from scalp eeg recordings using canonical cor-
1881 relation analysis, wavelets and random forests, *Clinical Neurophysiology* 128 (9) (2017) 1755–1769.
1882 doi:10.1016/j.clinph.2017.06.247.
1883 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1388245717304741>
- 1884 [118] U. Shah, M. Alzubaidi, F. Mohsen, A. Abd-Alrazaq, T. Alam, M. Househ, The role of artificial
1885 intelligence in decoding speech from eeg signals: A scoping review, *Sensors* 22 (18) (2022) 6975.
- 1886 [119] C. Y. Sai, N. Mokhtar, H. Arof, P. Cumming, M. Iwahashi, Automated classification and removal of
1887 eeg artifacts with svm and wavelet-ica, *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics* 22 (3)
1888 (2018) 664–670. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2017.2723420.
1889 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7968274/>
- 1890 [120] T. Radiuntz, J. Scouten, O. Hochmuth, B. Meffert, Automated eeg artifact elimination by applying
1891 machine learning algorithms to ica-based features, *Journal of Neural Engineering* 14 (4) (2017-08-01).
1892 doi:10.1088/1741-2552/aa69d1.
1893 URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1741-2552/aa69d1>
- 1894 [121] M. Mathe, M. Padmaja, B. T. Krishna, Intelligent approach for artifacts removal from eeg signal using
1895 heuristic-based convolutional neural network, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 70 (2021).
1896 doi:10.1016/j.bspc.2021.102935.
1897 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1746809421005322>
- 1898 [122] K. Yasoda, R. S. Ponnagal, K. S. Bhuvaneshwari, K. Venkatachalam, Automatic detection and classi-
1899 fication of eeg artifacts using fuzzy kernel svm and wavelet ica (wica), *Soft Computing* 24 (21) (2020)
1900 16011–16019. doi:10.1007/s00500-020-04920-w.
1901 URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00500-020-04920-w>
- 1902 [123] W. Ertel, *Introduction to Artificial Intelligence*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2017. doi:
1903 10.1007/978-3-319-58487-4.
- 1904 [124] G. Lee, S. Jin, J. An, Motion artifact correction of multi-measured functional near-infrared spec-
1905 troscopy signals based on signal reconstruction using an artificial neural network, *Sensors* 18 (9)
1906 (2018). doi:10.3390/s18092957.
1907 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/18/9/2957>
- 1908 [125] M. Sewak, S. K. Sahay, H. Rathore, An overview of deep learning architecture of deep neural networks
1909 and autoencoders, *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience* 17 (1) (2020-01-01) 182–
1910 188. doi:10.1166/jctn.2020.8648.
1911 URL <https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/10.1166/jctn.2020.8648>
- 1912 [126] *PhysioNet, Chb-mit scalp eeg database* (2010).
1913 URL <https://doi.org/10.13026/C2K01R>
- 1914 [127] D. Karaboga, E. Kaya, Adaptive network based fuzzy inference system (anfis) training approaches,
1915 *Artificial Intelligence Review* 52 (4) (2019) 2263–2293. doi:10.1007/s10462-017-9610-2.
1916 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10462-017-9610-2>
- 1917 [128] S. Salcedo-Sanz, J. L. Rojo-Álvarez, M. Martínez-Ramón, G. Camps-Valls, Support vector machines
1918 in engineering, *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* 4 (3) (2014)
1919 234–267. doi:10.1002/widm.1125.
1920 URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/widm.1125>

- 1921 [129] V. Lawhern, W. D. Hairston, K. McDowell, M. Westerfield, K. Robbins, Detection and classification
1922 of subject-generated artifacts in eeg signals using autoregressive models, *Journal of Neuroscience*
1923 *Methods* 208 (2) (2012) 181–189. doi:10.1016/j.jneumeth.2012.05.017.
1924 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0165027012001860>
- 1925 [130] P. Cunningham, S. J. Delany, K-nearest neighbour classifiers - a tutorial, *ACM Computing Surveys*
1926 54 (6) (2022-07-31) 1–25. doi:10.1145/3459665.
1927 URL <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3459665>
- 1928 [131] J. Gao, P. Lin, Y. Yang, P. Wang, C. Zheng, Real-time removal of ocular artifacts from eeg based on
1929 independent component analysis and manifold learning, *Neural Computing and Applications* 19 (8)
1930 (2010) 1217–1226. doi:10.1007/s00521-010-0370-z.
1931 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00521-010-0370-z>
- 1932 [132] T. S. Madhulatha, Comparison between k-means and k-medoids clustering algorithms, in: *Advances*
1933 *in Computing and Information Technology*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011, pp.
1934 472–481. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-22555-0_48.
1935 URL http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-642-22555-0_48
- 1936 [133] A. K. Maddirala, K. C. Veluvolu, Eye-blink artifact removal from single channel eeg with k-means
1937 and ssa, *Scientific Reports* 11 (1) (2021) 1–14. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-90437-7.
1938 URL <http://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-90437-7>
- 1939 [134] Z. Wang, C. Qin, B. Wan, W. W. Song, A comparative study of common nature-inspired algorithms
1940 for continuous function optimization, *Entropy* 23 (7) (2021). doi:10.3390/e23070874.
1941 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/23/7/874>
- 1942 [135] D. Karaboga, B. Gorkemli, C. Ozturk, N. Karaboga, A comprehensive survey, *Artificial Intelligence*
1943 *Review* 42 (1) (2014) 21–57. doi:10.1007/s10462-012-9328-0.
1944 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10462-012-9328-0>
- 1945 [136] M. Ahirwal, A. Kumar, G. Singh, Adaptive filtering of eeg/erp through bounded range artificial bee
1946 colony (br-abc) algorithm, *Digital Signal Processing* 25 (2014) 164–172. doi:10.1016/j.dsp.2013.
1947 10.019.
1948 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S105120041300239X>
- 1949 [137] D. Wang, D. Tan, L. Liu, Particle swarm optimization algorithm, *Soft Computing* 22 (2) (2018) 387–
1950 408. doi:10.1007/s00500-016-2474-6.
1951 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00500-016-2474-6>
- 1952 [138] M. K. Ahirwal, A. Kumar, G. K. Singh, Adaptive filtering of eeg/erp through noise cancellers using
1953 an improved pso algorithm, *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation* 14 (2014) 76–91. doi:10.1016/
1954 j.swevo.2013.10.001.
1955 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2210650213000564>
- 1956 [139] A. Faramarzi, M. Heidarinejad, S. Mirjalili, A. H. Gandomi, Marine predators algorithm, *Expert*
1957 *Systems with Applications* 152 (2020) 1–28. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2020.113377.
1958 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0957417420302025>
- 1959 [140] S. Yadav, S. Saha, R. Kar, D. Mandal, Eeg/erp signal enhancement through an optimally tuned
1960 adaptive filter based on marine predators algorithm, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 73
1961 (2022) 1–13. doi:10.1016/j.bspc.2021.103427.
1962 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1746809421010247>
- 1963 [141] G. Schalk, D. McFarland, T. Hinterberger, N. Birbaumer, J. Wolpaw, Bci2000, *IEEE Transactions on*
1964 *Biomedical Engineering* 51 (6) (2004) 1034–1043. doi:10.1109/TBME.2004.827072.
1965 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/1300799/>
- 1966 [142] A. Rezeika, M. Benda, P. Stawicki, F. Gembler, A. Saboor, I. Volosyak, Brain-computer interface
1967 spellers, *Brain Sciences* 8 (4) (2018) 1–38. doi:10.3390/brainsci8040057.
1968 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3425/8/4/57>
- 1969 [143] M. J. Vansteensel, E. G. Pels, M. G. Bleichner, M. P. Branco, T. Denison, Z. V. Freudenburg, P. Gos-
1970 selaar, S. Leinders, T. H. Ottens, M. A. Van Den Boom, et al., Fully implanted brain-computer
1971 interface in a locked-in patient with als, *New England Journal of Medicine* 375 (21) (2016) 2060–2066.

- 1972 [144] C. Haddix, A. F. Al-Bakri, S. Sunderam, Prediction of isometric handgrip force from graded event-
1973 related desynchronization of the sensorimotor rhythm, *Journal of Neural Engineering* 18 (5) (2021)
1974 056033.
- 1975 [145] D. Zhang, H. Song, R. Xu, W. Zhou, Z. Ling, B. Hong, Toward a minimally invasive brain-computer
1976 interface using a single subdural channel, *NeuroImage* 71 (2013) 30–41. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.
1977 2012.12.069.
1978 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1053811913000086>
- 1979 [146] T.-H. Nguyen, W.-Y. Chung, A single-channel ssvep-based bci speller using deep learning, *IEEE*
1980 *Access* 7 (2019) 1752–1763. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2886759.
1981 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8576511/>
- 1982 [147] H. K. Hamarashid, Modified long short-term memory and utilizing in building sequential model,
1983 *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research* 9 (2021) 207–211. doi:10.14741/
1984 *ijmcr/v.9.3.2*.
- 1985 [148] M. Schreuder, A. Riccio, M. Riseti, S. Dähne, A. Ramsay, J. Williamson, D. Mattia, M. Tangermann,
1986 User-centered design in brain-computer interfaces—a case study, *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*
1987 59 (2) (2013) 71–80. doi:10.1016/j.artmed.2013.07.005.
1988 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0933365713001188>
- 1989 [149] S. B. Borgheai, J. McLinden, A. H. Zisk, S. I. Hosni, R. J. Deligani, M. Abtahi, K. Mankodiya,
1990 Y. Shahriari, Enhancing communication for people in late-stage als using an fmirs-based bci system,
1991 *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering* 28 (5) (2020) 1198–1207. doi:
1992 10.1109/TNSRE.2020.2980772.
1993 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9035644/>
- 1994 [150] D. Kurmanaviciute, A. Rantala, M. Jas, A. Valila, L. Parkkonen, Target of selective auditory attention
1995 can be robustly followed with meg, Preprint (2022) 1–21doi:10.1101/588491;.
1996 URL <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/588491v1.full>
- 1997 [151] K. Fawagreh, M. M. Gaber, E. Elyan, Random forests, *Systems Science & Control Engineering* 2 (1)
1998 (2014-01-21) 602–609. doi:10.1080/21642583.2014.956265.
1999 URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/21642583.2014.956265>
- 2000 [152] L. Rokach, O. Maimon, Decision trees, in: *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery Handbook*, Springer-
2001 Verlag, New York, 2005, pp. 165–192. doi:10.1007/0-387-25465-X_9.
2002 URL http://link.springer.com/10.1007/0-387-25465-X_9
- 2003 [153] M. R. H. M. Adnan, A. Sarkheyli, A. M. Zain, H. Haron, Fuzzy logic for modeling machining process,
2004 *Artificial Intelligence Review* 43 (3) (2015) 345–379. doi:10.1007/s10462-012-9381-8.
2005 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10462-012-9381-8>
- 2006 [154] B. Blankertz, K.-R. Muller, D. Krusienski, G. Schalk, J. Wolpaw, A. Schlogl, G. Pfurtscheller, J. Mil-
2007 lan, M. Schroder, N. Birbaumer, The bci competition iii, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and*
2008 *Rehabilitation Engineering* 14 (2) (2006) 153–159. doi:10.1109/TNSRE.2006.875642.
2009 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/1642757/>
- 2010 [155] A.-N. Sharkawy, Principle of neural network and its main types, *Journal of Advances in Applied &*
2011 *Computational Mathematics* 7 (2020-12-31) 8–19. doi:10.15377/2409-5761.2020.07.2.
2012 URL <https://www.avantipublishers.com/index.php/jaacm/article/view/851>
- 2013 [156] M. M. Bradley, P. J. Lang, International affective picture system, in: *Encyclopedia of Personality*
2014 *and Individual Differences*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2017, pp. 1–4. doi:10.1007/
2015 978-3-319-28099-8_42-1.
2016 URL http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-28099-8_42-1
- 2017 [157] C. Muhl, C. Jeunet, F. Lotte, Eeg-based workload estimation across affective contexts, *Frontiers in*
2018 *Neuroscience* 8 (2014-06-12) 1–15. doi:10.3389/fnins.2014.00114.
2019 URL <http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnins.2014.00114/abstract>
- 2020 [158] S. Koelstra, C. Muhl, M. Soleymani, J. S. Lee, A. Yazdani, T. Ebrahimi, T. Pun, A. Nijholt, I. Patras,
2021 Deap, *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 3 (1) (2012) 18–31. doi:10.1109/T-AFFC.2011.15.
2022 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5871728/>

- 2023 [159] K. Shah, H. Patel, D. Sanghvi, M. Shah, A comparative analysis of logistic regression, random forest
2024 and knn models for the text classification, *Augmented Human Research* 5 (1) (2020) 1–16. doi:
2025 10.1007/s41133-020-00032-0.
2026 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s41133-020-00032-0>
- 2027 [160] N. J. McDonald, W. Soussou, Quasar’s qstates cognitive gauge performance in the cognitive state
2028 assessment competition 2011, in: 2011 Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering
2029 in Medicine and Biology Society, IEEE, Boston, 2011, pp. 6542–6546. doi:10.1109/IEMBS.2011.
2030 6091614.
2031 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6091614/>
- 2032 [161] N. Padfield, J. Zabalza, H. Zhao, V. Masero, J. Ren, Eeg-based brain-computer interfaces using motor-
2033 imagery, *Sensors* 19 (6) (2019) 1–34. doi:10.3390/s19061423.
2034 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/19/6/1423>
- 2035 [162] D. Haslacher, K. Nasr, S. R. Soekadar, Advancing sensory neuroprosthetics using artificial brain
2036 networks, *Patterns* 2 (7) (2021).
- 2037 [163] N. Ban, C. Qu, D. Feng, J. Pan, A hybrid brain-computer interface for smart car control, in: *Human*
2038 *Brain and Artificial Intelligence: Third International Workshop, HBAI 2022, Held in Conjunction*
2039 *with IJCAI-ECAI 2022, Vienna, Austria, July 23, 2022, Revised Selected Papers, Springer, 2022, pp.*
2040 *135–147.*
- 2041 [164] C. Bielza, P. Larrañaga, Discrete bayesian network classifiers, *ACM Computing Surveys* 47 (1) (2014)
2042 1–43. doi:10.1145/2576868.
2043 URL <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2576868>
- 2044 [165] K. A. Dylag, W. Wiczorek, W. Bauer, P. Walecki, B. Bando, R. Martinek, A. Kawala-Sterniuk, Pilot
2045 study on analysis of electroencephalography signals from children with fasd with the implementation
2046 of naive bayesian classifiers, *Sensors* 22 (1) (2021) 103.
- 2047 [166] S. Ding, H. Zhao, Y. Zhang, X. Xu, R. Nie, Extreme learning machine, *Artificial Intelligence Review*
2048 44 (1) (2015) 103–115. doi:10.1007/s10462-013-9405-z.
2049 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10462-013-9405-z>
- 2050 [167] Y. Zhang, Y. Wang, G. Zhou, J. Jin, B. Wang, X. Wang, A. Cichocki, Multi-kernel extreme learning
2051 machine for eeg classification in brain-computer interfaces, *Expert Systems with Applications* 96 (2018)
2052 302–310. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2017.12.015.
2053 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0957417417308291>
- 2054 [168] X. Zhang, Q. Xiong, Y. Dai, X. Xu, G. Song, An ecog-based binary classification of bci using optimized
2055 extreme learning machine, *Complexity* 2020 (2020-06-30) 1–13. doi:10.1155/2020/2913019.
2056 URL <https://www.hindawi.com/journals/complexity/2020/2913019/>
- 2057 [169] Y. Chen, X. Zhao, X. Jia, Spectral-spatial classification of hyperspectral data based on deep belief
2058 network, *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing* 8 (6)
2059 (2015) 2381–2392. doi:10.1109/JSTARS.2015.2388577.
2060 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7018910/>
- 2061 [170] S. U. Amin, M. Alsulaiman, G. Muhammad, M. A. Bencherif, M. S. Hossain, Multilevel weighted
2062 feature fusion using convolutional neural networks for eeg motor imagery classification, *IEEE Access*
2063 7 (2019) 18940–18950. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2895688.
2064 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8629079/>
- 2065 [171] G. Xu, X. Shen, S. Chen, Y. Zong, C. Zhang, H. Yue, M. Liu, F. Chen, W. Che, A deep transfer
2066 convolutional neural network framework for eeg signal classification, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 112767–
2067 112776. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2930958.
2068 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8772136/>
- 2069 [172] K. K. Krishnan, K. P. Soman, Cnn based classification of motor imaginary using variational mode
2070 decomposed eeg-spectrum image, *Biomedical Engineering Letters* 11 (3) (2021) 235–247. doi:10.
2071 1007/s13534-021-00190-z.
2072 URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s13534-021-00190-z>
- 2073 [173] C. Xiang, L. Zhang, Y. Tang, W. Zou, C. Xu, Ms-capsnet, *IEEE Signal Processing Letters* 25 (12)

- 2074 (2018) 1850–1854. doi:10.1109/LSP.2018.2873892.
 2075 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8481393/>
- 2076 [174] K.-W. Ha, J.-W. Jeong, Motor imagery eeg classification using capsule networks, *Sensors* 19 (13)
 2077 (2019) 1–20. doi:10.3390/s19132854.
 2078 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/19/13/2854>
- 2079 [175] M. Rashid, M. Islam, N. Sulaiman, B. S. Bari, R. K. Saha, M. J. Hasan, Electroencephalography based
 2080 motor imagery movements classification using long short-term memory (lstm) based on deep learning
 2081 approach, *SN Applied Sciences* 2 (2) (2020) 1–7. doi:10.1007/s42452-020-2023-x.
 2082 URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s42452-020-2023-x>
- 2083 [176] N. Naseer, K.-S. Hong, Classification of functional near-infrared spectroscopy signals corresponding to
 2084 the right- and left-wrist motor imagery for development of a brain-computer interface, *Neuroscience*
 2085 *Letters* 553 (2013) 84–89. doi:10.1016/j.neulet.2013.08.021.
 2086 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0304394013007544>
- 2087 [177] J. Zhang, G. Sudre, X. Li, W. Wang, D. J. Weber, A. Bagic, Clustering linear discriminant analysis
 2088 for meg-based brain computer interfaces, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation*
 2089 *Engineering* 19 (3) (2011) 221–231. doi:10.1109/TNSRE.2011.2116125.
 2090 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5716680/>
- 2091 [178] R. Xu, N. Jiang, N. Mrachacz-Kersting, C. Lin, G. A. Prieto, J. C. Moreno, J. L. Pons, K. Dremstrup,
 2092 D. Farina, A closed-loop brain-computer interface triggering an active ankle-foot orthosis for inducing
 2093 cortical neural plasticity, *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 61 (7) (2014) 2092–2101.
 2094 doi:10.1109/TBME.2014.2313867.
 2095 URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6778774/>
- 2096 [179] A. Liu, K. Chen, Q. Liu, Q. Ai, Y. Xie, A. Chen, Feature selection for motor imagery eeg clas-
 2097 sification based on firefly algorithm and learning automata, *Sensors* 17 (11) (2017) 1–15. doi:
 2098 10.3390/s17112576.
 2099 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/11/2576>
- 2100 [180] H. Fang, J. Jin, I. Daly, X. Wang, Feature extraction method based on filter banks and riemannian
 2101 tangent space in motor-imagery bci, *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics* 26 (6) (2022)
 2102 2504–2514. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2022.3146274.
 2103 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9695272/>
- 2104 [181] Y. Chu, X. Zhao, Y. Zou, W. Xu, G. Song, J. Han, Y. Zhao, Decoding multiclass motor imagery
 2105 eeg from the same upper limb by combining riemannian geometry features and partial least squares
 2106 regression, *Journal of Neural Engineering* 17 (4) (2020-08-11). doi:10.1088/1741-2552/aba7cd.
 2107 URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1741-2552/aba7cd>
- 2108 [182] M. T. Sadiq, X. Yu, Z. Yuan, Z. Fan, A. U. Rehman, G. Li, G. Xiao, Motor imagery eeg signals
 2109 classification based on mode amplitude and frequency components using empirical wavelet transform,
 2110 *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 127678–127692. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2939623.
 2111 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8825825/>
- 2112 [183] C. Li, H. Yang, L. Cheng, Fugl-meyer hand motor imagination recognition for brain-computer in-
 2113 terfaces using only fnirs, *Complex & Intelligent Systems* 8 (2) (2022) 731–741. doi:10.1007/
 2114 s40747-020-00266-w.
 2115 URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s40747-020-00266-w>
- 2116 [184] Y. Shiraishi, Y. Kawahara, O. Yamashita, R. Fukuma, S. Yamamoto, Y. Saitoh, H. Kishima, T. Yanag-
 2117 isawa, Neural decoding of electroencephalographic signals using dynamic mode decomposition, *Journal*
 2118 *of Neural Engineering* 17 (3) (2020-05-28) 1–12. doi:10.1088/1741-2552/ab8910.
 2119 URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1741-2552/ab8910>
- 2120 [185] S. Chaudhary, S. Taran, V. Bajaj, S. Siuly, A flexible analytic wavelet transform based approach
 2121 for motor-imagery tasks classification in bci applications, *Computer Methods and Programs in*
 2122 *Biomedicine* 187 (2020) 1–8. doi:10.1016/j.cmpb.2020.105325.
 2123 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S016926071930505X>
- 2124 [186] P. Khan, M. F. Kader, S. M. R. Islam, A. B. Rahman, M. S. Kamal, M. U. Toha, K.-S. Kwak, Machine

- 2125 learning and deep learning approaches for brain disease diagnosis, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 37622–37655.
 2126 doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3062484.
 2127 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9363896/>
- [187] A. Jafarifarmand, M. A. Badamchizadeh, S. Khanmohammadi, M. A. Nazari, B. M. Tazehkand, A
 2128 new self-regulated neuro-fuzzy framework for classification of eeg signals in motor imagery bci, *IEEE*
 2129 *Transactions on Fuzzy Systems* 26 (3) (2018) 1485–1497. doi:10.1109/TFUZZ.2017.2728521.
 2130 URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7982748/>
- [188] L. Yao, B. Zhu, M. Shoaran, Fast and accurate decoding of finger movements from ecog through
 2132 riemannian features and modern machine learning techniques, *Journal of Neural Engineering* 19 (1)
 2133 (2022-02-25). doi:10.1088/1741-2552/ac4ed1.
 2134 URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1741-2552/ac4ed1>
- [189] X. Huang, Y. Xu, J. Hua, W. Yi, H. Yin, R. Hu, S. Wang, A review on signal processing approaches
 2136 to reduce calibration time in eeg-based brain-computer interface, *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 15 (2021-
 2137 8-19). doi:10.3389/fnins.2021.733546.
 2138 URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnins.2021.733546/full>
- [190] S. Mirjalili, A. H. Gandomi, S. Z. Mirjalili, S. Saremi, H. Faris, S. M. Mirjalili, Salp swarm algorithm,
 2140 *Advances in Engineering Software* 114 (2017) 163–191. doi:10.1016/j.advengsoft.2017.07.002.
 2141 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0965997816307736>
- [191] T. Sang-To, M. Hoang-Le, M. A. Wahab, T. Cuong-Le, An efficient planet optimization algo-
 2143 rithm for solving engineering problems, *Scientific Reports* 12 (1) (2022) 1–18. doi:10.1038/
 2144 s41598-022-12030-w.
 2145 URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-022-12030-w>
- [192] J.-Y. Kim, S.-M. Park, K.-E. Ko, K.-B. Sim, Optimal eeg channel selection for motor imagery bci
 2147 system using bps0 and ga, in: *Robot Intelligence Technology and Applications 2012*, Springer Berlin
 2148 Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2013, pp. 231–239. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-37374-9_23.
 2149 URL http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-642-37374-9_23
- [193] A. P. Buccino, H. O. Keles, A. Omurtag, B. He, Hybrid eeg-fnirs asynchronous brain-computer in-
 2151 terface for multiple motor tasks, *PLOS ONE* 11 (1) (2016-1-5) 1–16. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.
 2152 0146610.
 2153 URL <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0146610>
- [194] R. Li, D. Yang, F. Fang, K.-S. Hong, A. L. Reiss, Y. Zhang, Concurrent fnirs and eeg for brain function
 2155 investigation: a systematic, methodology-focused review, *Sensors* 22 (15) (2022) 5865.
- [195] Z. Liu, J. Shore, M. Wang, F. Yuan, A. Buss, X. Zhao, A systematic review on hybrid eeg/fnirs in
 2157 brain-computer interface, *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 68 (2021) 102595.
- [196] H. Khan, N. Naseer, A. Yazidi, P. K. Eide, H. W. Hassan, P. Mirtaheri, Analysis of human gait using
 2159 hybrid eeg-fnirs-based bci system: a review, *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience* 14 (2021) 613254.
- [197] M.-C. Corsi, M. Chavez, D. Schwartz, L. Hugueville, A. N. Khambhati, D. S. Bassett, F. D. V.
 2160 Fallani, Integrating eeg and meg signals to improve motor imagery classification in brain-computer
 2161 interface, *International Journal of Neural Systems* 29 (01) (2019-01-10) 1–12. doi:10.1142/
 2162 S0129065718500144.
 2163 URL <https://www.worldscientific.com/doi/abs/10.1142/S0129065718500144>
- [198] D. Gutiérrez, Using eeg/meg data of cognitive processes in brain-computer interfaces, in: *AIP Con-*
 2166 *ference Proceedings*, Vol. 1032, American Institute of Physics, 2008, pp. 31–36.
- [199] G. Deshpande, D. Rangaprakash, L. Oeding, A. Cichocki, X. P. Hu, A new generation of brain-
 2168 computer interfaces driven by discovery of latent eeg-fnri linkages using tensor decomposition, *Front-*
 2169 *iers in Neuroscience* 11 (2017-06-07) 1–13. doi:10.3389/fnins.2017.00246.
 2170 URL <http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnins.2017.00246/full>
- [200] A. Khalaf, E. Sejdic, M. Akcakaya, Common spatial pattern and wavelet decomposition for motor
 2172 imagery eeg-ftcd brain-computer interface, *Journal of Neuroscience Methods* 320 (2019) 98–106.
- [201] A. Frank, UCI Machine Learning Repository. Irvine, CA: University of California, School of Informa-
 2174 tion and Computer Science, <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml> (2010).
 2175

- 2176 [202] E. Barzegaran, S. Bosse, P. J. Kohler, A. M. Norcia, Eegsourcesim, Journal of Neuroscience Methods
2177 328 (2019) 1–36. doi:10.1016/j.jneumeth.2019.108377.
2178 URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0165027019302341>
- 2179 [203] J. A. Wilson, Massively parallel signal processing using the graphics processing unit for real-time
2180 brain-computer interface feature extraction, Frontiers in Neuroengineering 2 (2009) 1–13. doi:10.
2181 3389/neuro.16.011.2009.
2182 URL <http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/neuro.16.011.2009/abstract>